

Index and Queries for the Bibliometric Data of
the HICSS 2022 Submission: "Trends in
Academic and Industrial Research on Business
Process Management - A Computational
Literature Analysis"

Submitted on September 16, 2021

1 Queries used for Multidimensional Analysis

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-----  
-- (Q1) Table 1 (2005 - 2009)  
-----  
SELECT continent AS Continent,  
       Count(DISTINCT f.doi) AS n_papers  
FROM   f_dblp f  
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa  
                ON f.doi = dpa.doi  
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou  
                ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id  
       INNER JOIN d_institution din  
                ON f.institution_id = din.institution_id  
       INNER JOIN d_country dco  
                ON din.institution_country_id = dco.country_id  
WHERE  year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2009  
GROUP BY continent;  
  
-----  
-- (Q2) Table 1 (2010 - 2014)  
-----  
SELECT continent AS Continent,  
       Count(DISTINCT f.doi) AS n_papers  
FROM   f_dblp f  
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa  
                ON f.doi = dpa.doi  
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou  
                ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id  
       INNER JOIN d_institution din  
                ON f.institution_id = din.institution_id  
       INNER JOIN d_country dco  
                ON din.institution_country_id = dco.country_id  
WHERE  year BETWEEN 2010 AND 2014  
GROUP BY continent;  
  
-----  
-- (Q3) Table 1 (2015 - 2019)  
-----  
SELECT continent AS Continent,  
       Count(DISTINCT f.doi) AS n_papers  
FROM   f_dblp f  
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa  
                ON f.doi = dpa.doi  
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou  
                ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id  
       INNER JOIN d_institution din  
                ON f.institution_id = din.institution_id  
       INNER JOIN d_country dco  
                ON din.institution_country_id = dco.country_id  
WHERE  year BETWEEN 2015 AND 2019  
GROUP BY continent;
```

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-----  
-- (Q4) Table 1 (2005 - 2019)  
-----
```

```
SELECT continent AS Continent,  
       Count(DISTINCT f.doi) AS n_papers  
FROM   f_dblp f  
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa  
             ON f.doi = dpa.doi  
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou  
             ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id  
       INNER JOIN d_institution din  
             ON f.institution_id = din.institution_id  
       INNER JOIN d_country dco  
             ON din.institution_country_id = dco.country_id  
WHERE  year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2019  
GROUP BY continent;
```

```
-----  
-- (Q5) Table 2 (average paper / author)  
-----
```

```
SELECT Avg(cnt) AS avg_paper_per_author  
FROM   (SELECT Count(DISTINCT f.doi) AS cnt  
        FROM   d_author aut  
              INNER JOIN f_dblp f  
                    ON f.author_id = aut.author_id  
              INNER JOIN d_paper p  
                    ON f.doi = p.doi  
        WHERE  p.year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2019  -- options (different periods)  
        GROUP BY f.author_id) AS first;
```

```
-----  
-- (Q6) Table 2 (average authors / paper)  
-----
```

```
SELECT Avg(groupn)  
FROM   (SELECT f.doi,  
              title,  
              Count(DISTINCT f.author_id) AS groupn  
        FROM   d_author aut  
              INNER JOIN f_dblp f  
                    ON f.author_id = aut.author_id  
              INNER JOIN d_paper p  
                    ON f.doi = p.doi  
              INNER JOIN d_institution i  
                    ON i.institution_id = f.institution_id  
              INNER JOIN d_outlet o  
                    ON o.outlet_id = f.outlet_id  
        WHERE  p.year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2019  -- options (different periods)  
        GROUP BY f.doi,  
              title  
        ORDER BY f.doi,  
              title DESC) AS t;
```

```

-----
-- (Q7) Table 2 (n authors)
-----
SELECT Count(DISTINCT author_id) AS n_author
FROM   f_dblp f
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa
                ON f.doi = dpa.doi
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou
                ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id
WHERE  year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2019;      -- options (different periods)

-----
-- (Q8) Table 3 (n authors)
-----
SELECT Count(DISTINCT author_name)
FROM   f_dblp f
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa
                ON f.doi = dpa.doi
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou
                ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id
       INNER JOIN d_institution din
                ON f.institution_id = din.institution_id
       INNER JOIN d_country dco
                ON din.institution_country_id = dco.country_id
       INNER JOIN d_author aut
                ON aut.author_id = f.author_id
WHERE  institution_category = 0          -- options (0, 1, 2, 3)
       AND year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2019;  -- options (different periods)

-----
-- (Q9) Table 3 (n papers )
-----
SELECT Count(DISTINCT dpa.doi)
FROM   f_dblp f
       INNER JOIN d_paper dpa
                ON f.doi = dpa.doi
       INNER JOIN d_outlet dou
                ON f.outlet_id = dou.outlet_id
       INNER JOIN d_institution din
                ON f.institution_id = din.institution_id
       INNER JOIN d_country dco
                ON din.institution_country_id = dco.country_id
       INNER JOIN d_author aut
                ON aut.author_id = f.author_id
WHERE  institution_category = 0          -- options (0, 1, 2, 3)
       AND year BETWEEN 2005 AND 2019;  -- options (different periods)

```

2 List of Stopwords for Data Clearing

based	2019	doi.
editorial	2020	doi:
guest	received	issn
label	received:	issn:
section	revised	softw
paper	revised:	syst
cluster	accepted	figure
using	accepted:	fig
special	published	fig.
http	published:	table
https	online	tab
www	springer	tab.
uhihuhqfh	verlag	rtu
january	berlin	ifip
february	heidelberg	poem
march	acm	BPMS
june	ieee	BMSD
july	csimq	ER
august	bpm	EMISA
september	conference	Sosym
october	keywords	IJISMD
september	keywords.	process
november	abstract	international
december	abstract.	
2004	introduction	
2005	foundations	
2006	conclusion	
2007	description	
2008	complex	
2009	article	
2010	issue	
2011	issue:	
2012	vol	
2013	vol.	
2014	no	
2015	no.	
2016	pages	
2017	press	
2018	doi	

3 Authors and Institution Assignments

author_name	institution	category
A. A. Ageev	National Research University Higher School of Economics	0
A. Dreiling	University of Münster	0
A. F. Vincent	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
A. J. M. M. Weijters	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
A. J. Moleman	University of Amsterdam	0
A. Mos	Institut national de recherche en informatique et en automatique	1
A. Selcuk Guceglioglu	Middle East Technical University	0
Aaron Kunde	University of Potsdam	0
Abderrahmane Maaradji	National ICT Australia	1
Abel Armas-Cervantes	University of Tartu	0
Abel Armas-Cervantes	The University of Melbourne	0
Abrehet M. Omer	Technical University Dresden	0
Abubakar Sadiq Sani	The University of Sydney	0
Achim D. Brucker	SAP Germany	2
Achim Strauss	Ulm University	0
Adela del-Río-Ortega	University of Seville	0
Ademar Aguiar	Universidade do Porto	0
Aditya K. Ghose	University of Wollongong	0
Adnene Guabtni	UMR LORIA	1
Adnene Guabtni	University Henri Poincaré (Nancy 1)	0
Adrian Flatgard	IBM Research United States	1
Adrian Giurca	Brandenburg Technical University at Cottbus	0
Adrian Holfter	University of Potsdam	0
Adrian Iordachescu	Shared Web Services Pty Ltd	2
Adrian Manresa	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Adrian Mocan	National University of Ireland	0
Adrian Paschke	Freie Universität Berlin	0
Adrian Rebmann	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Adriano Augusto	The University of Melbourne	0

Adriano Augusto	University of Tartu	0
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Agnes Koschmider	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Agnes Koschmider	University of Karlsruhe	0
Agnès Front	Grenoble University	0
Ahmed Awad	University of Potsdam	0
Ahmed Awad	Cairo University	0
Ahmed Kheldoun	University Of Science And Technology Houari Boumediene	0
Ahmet Coşkunçay	Middle East Technical University	0
Ahmet Dikici	TÜBİTAK BİLGEM Software Technologies Research Institute	1
Aitor Murguzur	IK4-Ikerlan Research Center	1
Akhil Kumar	The Pennsylvania State University	0
Akiyoshi Matono	Grid Technology Research Center	1
Alan Colman	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Alan Fekete	The University of Sydney	0
Albert Eckert	Siemens AG	2
Albert Fleischmann	Metasonic AG	2
Alberto Manuel	Process Sphere	2
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Aldinei Bastos	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Alejandro Buchmann	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
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Alejandro Vaisman	Universidad de Chile	0
Aleksandar Vranesevic	University of Wollongong	0
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Alessandro Costa Pereira	SAP Germany	2

Alessandro Gabiadini	University of Milano-Bicocca	0
Alessandro Gianola	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Alessandro Russo	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Alessandro Sperduti	University of Padova	0
Alessandro Stefanini	University of Pisa	0
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Alex Kass	Accenture Technology Labs	1
Alex Kokkonen	Johnson & Johnson	2
Alex Seret	KU Leuven	1
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Alexander Chambers	Defence Science and Technology Group	2
Alexander De Craemer	KU Leuven	1
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Alexander Serebrenik	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
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Armando Ordonez		University Foundation of Popayán	0
Armin Stein		European Research Center for Information Systems	1
Armin Stein		University of Münster	0
Armin Zimmermann	Zimmer-	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Arnas Kaceni- auskas	Kaceni-	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University	0
Arne-Jørgen Berre		SINTEF	1
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Artem Polyvyanyy		The University of Melbourne	0
Artem Polyvyanyy		University of Potsdam	0
Artem Polyvyanyy		Queensland University of Technology	0
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Avi Wasser	ProcessGene Ltd.	2
Avi Wasser	Israel Institute of Technology	1
Avigdor Gal	Technion–Israel Institute of Technology	1
Avishai Mandelbaum	Technion–Israel Institute of Technology	1
Avner Ottensooser	The University of Sydney	0
Awais Rashid	Lancaster University	0
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Axel Heßler	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Axel Kieninger	University of Karlsruhe	0
Axel Martens	IBM Research United States	1
Axel Polleres	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Axel Winkelmann	University of Würzburg	0
Ayelet Goldstein	Ben Gurion University of the Negev	0
Aygun Shafagatova	Ghent University	0
Azalia Shamsaei	University of Ottawa	0
B. Luka	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
B. Pernici	Politecnico di Milano	0
Babak Bagheri Hariri	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Babis Magoutas	National Technical University of Athens	0
Bandar Alhaqbani	Information Security Institute	1
Banu Aysolmaz	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Banu Aysolmaz	Maastricht University	0
Barbara Dinter	Chemnitz University of Technology	0
Barbara Jobstmann	EPF Lausanne	0
Barbara Keller	Hochschule München	0
Barbara Keller	Hochschule Aalen	0
Barbara Paech	University of Heidelberg	0
Barbara Pernici	Politecnico di Milano	0
Barbara Pes	University of Cagliari	0
Barbara Re	University of Camerino	0
Barbara Thönssen	University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW)	0
Barbara Vögeli	University of Bern	0
Barbara Weber	University of Innsbruck	0

Barbara Weber	Technical University of Denmark	0
Barbara Weber	Universits of Innsbruck	0
Barry Norton	The Open University	0
Bart Baesens	KU Leuven	1
Bart Franciscus Antonius Hompes	Philips Research	1
Bart Orriëns	Tilburg University	0
Bastian Wurm	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Bela Mutschler	Ravensburg-Weingarten University of Applied Sciences	0
Bela Mutschler	University of Applied Sciences Ravensburg-Weingarten	0
Bela Mutschler	Trier University of Applied Science	0
Belhassen Zouari	University of Tunis El Manar	0
Ben Jennings	University College London	0
Benjamin Jochum	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Benjamin Kloemper	ABB AG	2
Benjamin Satzger	Vienna University of Technology	0
Benjamin Ulm	University of Potsdam	0
Benoît Depaire	Hasselt University	0
Berardino de Bari	Centre Hospitalier Régional Universitaire Jean Minjoz	0
Bernardo N. Yahya	Pusan National University	0
Bernardo Oliveira Pinto	INESC-ID	1
Bernardo Valdivieso	Hospital Universitario y Politécnico de La Fe	0
Bernd Michelberger	University of Applied Sciences Ravensburg-Weingarten	0
Bernd Michelberger	Trier University of Applied Science	0
Bernhard M. Turban	University of Applied Sciences RheinMain	0
Bernhard Selk	University of Augsburg	0
Bernhard Volz	University of Bayreuth	0
Berny Carrera	Kyung Hee University	0
Bertram Ludäscher	University of California Davis	0
Beth Plale	Indiana University	0
Bettina Bazijanec	University of Augsburg	0
Bettina Hermes	Saarland University	0

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Bing Bing Zhou	The University of Sydney	0
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Birger Andersson	Stockholm University	0
Birger Andersson	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	0
Birger Lantow	University of Rostock	0
Birgit Burmeister	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Birgit Hofreiter	Liechtenstein University	0
Björn Bergh	University Hospital Heidelberg	0
Björn Rafn Gunnarsson	KU Leuven	1
Bo Hu	SAP Germany	2
Bogdan Franczyk	University of Leipzig	0
Borja Vázquez-Barreiros	University of Santiago de Compostela	0
Boualem Benatalah	The University of New South Wales	0
Boudewijn F. van Dongen	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Branimir Wetzein	University of Stuttgart	0
Brian Elvesæter	SINTEF	1
Bruce Hamilton	National Research Council Canada, Fredericton	1
Bruna Diirr	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Bruno Bellovoda	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Bruno Defude	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Bruno F. Mazza	Hospital Samaritano de São Paulo	3
Burkhard Kittl	Vienna University of Technology	0
Byoung Kyu Choi	Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology	1
Byung-Hyun Ha	Pusan National University	0
Byung-Kwan Choi	Pusan National University Hospital	0
Byungduk Jeong	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Bénédicte Le Grand	Panthéon-Sorbonne University (Paris I)	0
Bénédicte Le Grand	Université Pierre et Marie Curie (Paris VI)	0
Cagdas Gereade	University of California at Santa Barbara	0
Calton Pu	Georgia Institute of Technology	1
Camilla Bomfim	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Camilo Flores	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0

Carla Simone	University of Milano-Bicocca	0
Carles Pairot	Universitat Rovira i Virgili	0
Carlo Combi	University of Verona	0
Carlo Simon	University of Koblenz-Landau	0
Carlos Delgado-Kloos	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid	0
Carlos Fernández-Llatas	Universitat Politècnica de València	0
Carlos Hurtado	Universidad de Chile	0
Carlos Rodríguez	University of Trento	0
Carmelo Del Valle	University of Seville	0
Carmen Vaca	Politecnico di Milano	0
Carolin Berhalter	University of Applied Sciences Würzburg-Schweinfurt	0
Carolina Ming Chiao	Ulm University	0
Carsten Cordes	University of Oldenburg	0
Carsten Felden	University for Mining and Technology of Freiberg	0
Carsten Maletzki	University of Trier	0
Carsten Rothballer	ICLEI Europe	1
Casper Stoel	Pallas Athena	2
Cassio Melo	École Centrale Paris	0
Cesar Meneses	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Cesare Pautasso	University of Lugano	0
Chang Heng	Huawei Technologies	2
Charalampos C. Alevizos	City, University of London	0
Charles Møller	Aalborg University	0
Charlotte Wehking	Liechtenstein University	0
Chathura C. Ekanayake	WSO2	2
Chathura C. Ekanayake	Queensland University of Technology	0
Chen Li	University of Twente	0
Chengfei Liu	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Chiao-Yun Li	Fraunhofer-Institut für Angewandte Informationstechnik FIT	1
Chiara Di Francescomarino	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	1
Chiara Ghidini	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	1
Chiara Muzi	University of Camerino	0

Chihab Hanachi	University Toulouse 1 (Toulouse 1)	0
Chihiro Suematsu	Kyoto University	0
Chris Turner	Cranfield University	0
Christian Allmann	AUDI AG	2
Christian Brelage	SAP Germany	2
Christian Buddendick	University of Münster	0
Christian Flender	Queensland University of Technology	0
Christian Gerth	University of Paderborn	0
Christian Gerth	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Christian Haisjackl	University of Innsbruck	0
Christian Janiesch	University of Würzburg	0
Christian Janiesch	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Christian Janiesch	Technical University Dresden	0
Christian Janiesch	European Research Center for Information Systems	1
Christian M. Schweda	LeanIT42 GmbH	2
Christian Pichler	Research Studios Austria Forschungsgesellschaft mbH	1
Christian Stahl	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Christian Stahl	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Christian Stamber	IDS Scheer AG	2
Christian Stary	Johannes Kepler University Linz	0
Christian Sturm	University of Bayreuth	0
Christian Thiemich	Bosch Software Innovations GmbH	2
Christian Toinard	École nationale supérieure d'ingénieurs	0
Christian W. Günther	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Christian W. Günther	Fluxicon	2
Christian Wakup	rubecon information technologies GmbH	2
Christian Wolter	SAP Germany	2
Christiane Jungius	HES-SO Valais	0
Christin Seifert	University of Twente	0
Christina Tsagakani	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)	0
Christoffer Olling Back	University of Copenhagen	0

Christoph Außen	RWTH Aachen University	0
Christoph Briem	RWTH Aachen University	0
Christoph Cewe	E.ON IT UK Limited	2
Christoph Czepa	University of Vienna	0
Christoph Dorn	Vienna University of Technology	0
Christoph Dorn	University of California at Irvine	0
Christoph Kollwitz	Chemnitz University of Technology	0
Christoph Meinel	University of Potsdam	0
Christoph P. Neumann	Friedrich-Alexander University Nürnberg	0
Christoph Ringelstein	University of Koblenz-Landau	0
Christoph Rinner	Medical University of Vienna	0
Christoph Rosenkranz	University of Frankfurt	0
Christoph Ruh-sam	ISIS-Papyrus	2
Christoph Schütz	Johannes Kepler University Linz	0
Christophe Incoul	Centre d'Innovation par les Technologies de l'Information(CITI), Centre de Recherche Public Henri Tudor	1
Christophe Marsala	UMR LIP6	1
Christopher Hahn	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Christopher John Davis	Technical University of Denmark	0
Christopher Klinkmüller	CSIRO	1
Christopher Klinkmüller	University of Leipzig	0
Christopher Reichstein	Hochschule Aalen	0
Christos Douligeris	University of Piraeus	0
Chul Young Kim	Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology	1
Chun Hua Tian	IBM Research United States	1
Chun Ouyang	Queensland University of Technology	0
Ciarán McInerney	University of Leeds	0
Clara Ayora	Universitat Politècnica de València	0
Clarence A. Ellis	University of Colorado	0
Claude Godart	UMR LORIA	1
Claudia Cappelli	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0

Claudia Diamantini	Marche Polytechnic University	0
Claudia d'Amato	University of Bari	0
Claudia Maria Lima Werner	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Claudia Picardi	University of Torino	0
Claudia Reuter	Zühlke AG	2
Claudio Bartolini	Hewlett Packard Labs	1
Claudio Di Ciccio	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Clay Richardson	Forrester Research	1
Clemilson Luís de Brito Dias	Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul	0
Cláudia Alves	Technical University of Lisbon	0
Colin J. Fidge	Queensland University of Technology	0
Conrad Indiono	University of Vienna	0
Constantin Houy	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Constantin Houy	Saarland University	0
Cornelia Haisjackl	University of Innsbruck	0
Costas Patsakis	University of Piraeus	0
Craig A. Bunnell	Dana-Farber Cancer Institute	1
Craig Kuziemyky	University of Ottawa	0
Cristhian Figueroa	University of Cauca	0
Cristina Baroglio	University of Torino	0
Cristina Cabanillas	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Cristina Cabanillas	University of Seville	0
Cristina Campos	Universitat Jaume I	0
Cuicui Ji	Hefei University of Technology	0
Cátia Pesquita	University of Lisbon	0
Cédric Delvaux	KU Leuven	1
Cédric Favre	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Célia Ghedini Ralha	University of Brasilia	0
Célia Ghedini Ralha	Universidade de Brasília (UnB)	0
César A. Marín	University of Manchester	0
D. Aissani	University of Bejaia	0
D. Borrego	University of Seville	0
D. Lombardi	Politecnico di Milano	0

D. M. M. Schunseelaar	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Dan Bogdanov	Cybernetica AS	2
Daniel Amyot	University of Ottawa	0
Daniel Beimborn	Frankfurt School of Finance & Management	0
Daniel Capurro	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Daniel Faria	Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciencia	1
Daniel Felipe Rivas	University of Cauca	0
Daniel Gillblad	Swedish Institute of Computer Science	1
Daniel Koch	Valeroo GmbH	2
Daniel Metz	University of Siegen	0
Daniel Pfeiffer	European Research Center for Information Systems	1
Daniel Reißner	University of Augsburg	0
Daniel Reißner	The University of Melbourne	0
Daniel Schall	Vienna University of Technology	0
Daniel V. Oppenheim	IBM Research United States	1
Daniel Wutke	University of Stuttgart	0
Daniela Grigori	Université Paris-Saclay	0
Daniela Loreti	University of Bologna	0
Daniela Luengo	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Daniela Rosca	Monmouth University	0
Daniela Weinberg	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Daniele Sora	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Daniele Theseider Dupré	University of Eastern Piedmont	0
Danilo Ardagna	Politecnico di Milano	0
Danilo Montesi	University of Bologna	0
Danny Ammon	Technische Universität Ilmenau	0
Danny Ting-Yi Ho	Howe School of Technology Management	0
Dario Lötscher	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Darkhan Mukhatov	“Zerde” Holding JSC	2
Dave Green	Microsoft Corporate Campus	1
David Baumgartner	University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria	0
David Carrera	Technical University of Catalonia	0
David Chapela-Campa	University of Santiago de Compostela	0
David Cohn	IBM Research United States	1
David Edmond	Queensland University of Technology	0

David Grünert	ZHAW School of Management and Law	0
David Harel	Weizmann Institute of Science	1
David Hogg	University of Leeds	0
David Knuplesch	Ulm University	0
David Langer	Ulm University	0
David Leake	Indiana University	0
David Levy	The University of Sydney	0
David Martens	KU Leuven	1
David Martinho	ESW Software Engineering Group	2
David Martinho	Technical University of Lisbon	0
David Martinho	INOV	1
David Redlich	SAP Research United Kingdom	1
David Richard Schäfer	University of Stuttgart	0
David S. Corchuelo	University of Cauca	0
David Sánchez-Charles	CA Strategic Research, CA Technologies	1
David W. Glasspool	University of Edinburgh	0
David Winkel	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	0
Davide Aloini	University of Pisa	0
Davide Rossi	University of Bologna	0
Davood Astaraky	University of Ottawa	0
Debdoot Mukherjee	IBM Research India	1
Dennis Bokermann	University of Paderborn	0
Dennis M. Riehle	University of Münster	0
Dennis Wegener	Fraunhofer-Institut für Intelligente Analyse- und Informationssysteme IAIS	1
Denny Vrandečić	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Despina Topali	Harokopio University of Athens	0
Detlef Köntges	Ulm University	0
Detlef Seese	University of Karlsruhe	0
Diana Heckl	Frankfurt School of Finance & Management	0
Diana Puentes	Universidad de los Andes	0
Diego Calvanese	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Diego Liberati	CNR IEIIT	1
Dierk A. Vagts	University of Rostock	0
Dierk Jugel	Reutlingen University	0
Dilian Gurov	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	0

Dimitris Apostolou	National Technical University of Athens	0
Dimitris Apostolou	University of Piraeus	0
Dimka Karastoyanova	University of Stuttgart	0
Dimka Karastoyanova	University of Groningen	0
Dimosthenis Anagnostopoulos	Harokopio University of Athens	0
Dina Bayomie	Cairo University	0
Dina Satybaldina	L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University	0
Dingxian Wang	East China Normal University	0
Diogo R. Ferreira	Technical University of Lisbon	0
Diogo R. Ferreira	University of Lisbon	0
Dirk Ahlers	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
Dirk Budke	UMB AG	2
Dirk Deschoolmeester	Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School	0
Dirk Fahland	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Dirk Fahland	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Dirk Hageböling	Civil Defence Authority	3
Dirk Hoffmann	medrapid GmbH	2
Dirk Werth	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Divya Kundra	Indraprastha Institute of Information Technology, Delhi (IIITD)	1
Dmitrij Olifer	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University	0
Domenico Corapi	Imperial College London	0
Domenico Potena	Marche Polytechnic University	0
Domenico Saccà	University of Calabria	0
Dominic Breuker	University of Münster	0
Dominic Breuker	WWU Muenster - ERCIS	1
Dominic Greenwood	Whitestein Technologies AG	2
Dominic Müller	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Dominic Müller	Ulm University	0
Dominic Müller	University of Twente	0
Dominik Kuropka	Hasso-Plattner-Institute	1
Dominik Riemer	FZI Research Center for Information Technologies	1
Dominique Rieu	Grenoble University	0
Donald F. Ferguson	IBM Research United States	1

Donato Malerba	University of Bari	0
Dong Hun Kang	Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology	1
Dong Yuan	The University of Sydney	0
Douglas Alves Peixoto	Universidade Federal de Viçosa	0
Drakoulis Markatos	University of Athens	0
Dries Couckuyt	Ghent University	0
Duckwoong Lee	Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology	1
Débora Maria Paiva	Computing College, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS)	0
E. Mussi	Politecnico di Milano	0
Ealan Henis	IBM Research Israel	1
Eddy Truyen	KU Leuven	1
Edilson Palma	Computing College, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS)	0
Eduardo A. P. Santos	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Eduardo de F.R. Loures	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Eduardo Fernández-Medina	University of Castilla-La Mancha	0
Eduardo González López de Murillas	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Eduardo Neves	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Egon Börger	University of Pisa	0
Ehab Ezat	Cairo University	0
Ehsan Roohi Gohar	Queensland University of Technology	0
Eitam Sheerit	Technion–Israel Institute of Technology	1
Ekaterina Bazhenova	University of Potsdam	0
Ekkart Kindler	University of Paderborn	0
Ekkehard Finkeisen	medrapid GmbH	2
Elena Hernando	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	0
Elena Kushnareva	Panthéon-Sorbonne University (Paris I)	0
Elham Ramezani	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Elham Ramezani	Hochschule Furtwangen	0
Elio Damaggio	University of California at San Diego	0
Elior Ariel	Ben Gurion University of the Negev	0

Elisa Marengo	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Elisa Yumi Nakagawa	University of São Paulo	0
Elisabetta Benvenuto	Tor Vergata University of Rome	0
Elke Brucker-Kley	ZHAW School of Management and Law	0
Elske Ammenwerth	University for Health Sciences, Medical Informatics and Technology (UMIT)	0
Emil Lupu	Imperial College London	0
Emilia Cimpian	National University of Ireland	0
Emilian Pascalau	University of Potsdam	0
Emiliano Reynares	Universidad Tecnológica Naciona	0
Emilio Sulis	University of Torino	0
Emma Bosley	Queensland Ambulance Service (QAS)	3
Emmanuel Helm	University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria	0
Eng Chew	University of Technology	0
Enric Brull	Diputació de Tarragona	3
Enrico Graupner	University of Mannheim	0
Eran Toch	Technion–Israel Institute of Technology	1
Erdem Eser Ekinici	Galaksiya Bilişim Teknolojileri	2
Erez Shalom	Ben Gurion University of the Negev	0
Erhard Weiss	ISIS-Papyrus	2
Eric Andonoff	University Toulouse 1 (Toulouse 1)	0
Eric Dubois	Centre d’Innovation par les Technologies de l’Information(CITI), Centre de Recherche Public Henri Tudor	1
Eric Rietzke	Trier University of Applied Sciences	0
Eric Rietzschel	University of Groningen	0
Eric Rojas	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Eric Verbeek	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Erica French	Queensland University of Technology	0
Erich Ortner	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Erich Schikuta	University of Vienna	0
Erik H. J. Nooijen	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Erik Perjons	Stockholm University	0
Erik Smit	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Erin Stretton	Philips Research	1
Ernest Teniente	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Ernesto Damiani	Khalifa University of Science and Technology	0
Ernesto Damiani	University of Milan	0
Ernst Kreuzer	Campus 02 University of Applied Sciences	0

Estefanía Serral	KU Leuven	1
Etienne Fux	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Eva Bucherer	University of St. Gallen	0
Eva L. Klijn	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Evelina Lamma	University of Ferrara	0
F. Calore	Politecnico di Milano	0
F. Lecue	University of Manchester	0
Fabian Pittke	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Fabian Pittke	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Fabian Stäber	Siemens AG	2
Fabiana Fournier	IBM Research Israel	1
Fabienne Lam- busch	University of Rostock	0
Fabio Aioli	University of Padova	0
Fabio Casati	University of Trento	0
Fabio Martinelli	Istituto di Informatica e Telematica Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	1
Fabio Patrizi	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Fabio Vitali	University of Bologna	0
Fabrizio Maria Maggi	University of Tartu	0
Fabrizio Maria Maggi	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Fabrizio Riguzzi	University of Ferrara	0
Fahim Imam	St. Francis Xavier University	0
Fahri Buğra Çam- lıca	Başkent University	0
Faiz UL Muram	University of Vienna	0
Faiza Allah Bukhsh	University of Twente	0
Falko Koetter	University of Stuttgart	0
Farbod Taymouri	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Farouk Toumani	Blaise Pascal University	0
Faruk Hasić	KU Leuven	1
Fathi M. Al- Ghaiati	Alexandria University	0
Fatma Pakdil	Başkent University	0
Fco. Fernando de la Rosa Troyano	University of Seville	0
Federica Durante	University of Milano-Bicocca	0
Federica Pochiero	University of Pisa	0
Federico Cabitza	University of Milano-Bicocca	0

Federico Capuzzimati	University of Torino	0
Federico Chesani	University of Bologna	0
Fei Wang	IBM Research United States	1
Felix Flentge	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Felix Jonathan Oppermann	University of Lübeck	0
Felix Kosmalla	Saarland University	0
Felix Mannhardt	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Felix Mannhardt	SINTEF	1
Felix Reher	University of the West of Scotland	0
Felix Wortmann	University of St. Gallen	0
Feng Gao	National University of Ireland	0
Fenno F. (Terry) Heath	IBM Research United States	1
Fenno F. Heath III	IBM Research United States	1
Fernanda Araujo Baião	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Fernanda Gonzalez-Lopez	Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso	0
Fernando Szimanski	Universidade de Brasília (UnB)	0
Fethi A. Rabhi	The University of New South Wales	0
Filip Caron	KU Leuven	1
Filipe Esteves Gonçalves	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Filippo Ramoni	Politecnico di Milano	0
Flavio Corradini	University of Camerino	0
Florian A. Herzog	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Florian Bär	Hochschule München	0
Florian Daniel	University of Trento	0
Florian Evequoz	HES-SO Valais	0
Florian Gottschalk	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Florian Imgrund	University of Würzburg	0
Florian Matthes	Technische Universität München	0
Florian Pinel	IBM Research United States	1
Florian Richter	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	0
Florian Rittmeier	Paderborn University	0
Florian Schnabel	University of St. Gallen	0
Florian Schnabel	SAP Research Switzerland	1
Florian Strecker	Metasonic AG	2
Flávia Santoro	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0

Fouzia Ounnar	Université Paul Cézanne	0
Fran Casino	University of Piraeus	0
Francesca Marazza	University of Genoa	0
Francesca Zerbato	University of Verona	0
Francesca Zerbato	University of Potsdam	0
Francesco Folino	CNR ICAR	1
Francesco Leotta	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Francesco Tiezzi	University of Camerino	0
Francisco Curbera	IBM Research United States	1
Franco Arcieri	Tor Vergata University of Rome	0
Francois Habryn	University of Karlsruhe	0
Frank Dengler	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Frank Dengler	University of Karlsruhe	0
Frank Fox	University of Leeds	0
Frank J. H. M. van den Biggelaar	Maastricht University	0
Frank Leymann	University of Stuttgart	0
Frank Puhlmann	University of Potsdam	0
Frank Puhlmann	Bosch Software Innovations GmbH	2
Frank Ruwolt	Fraunhofer-Institut für Intelligente Analyse- und Informationssysteme IAIS	1
Frank van Geffen	Rabobank	2
Frank van Harmelen	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
François Charoy	UMR LORIA	1
François Charoy	Université de Lorraine	0
François Charoy	University Henri Poincaré (Nancy 1)	0
Freddie Van Rijswijk	ISIS-Papyrus	2
Frederick Benaben	Université de Toulouse	0
Frederick Wu	IBM Research United States	1
Frederik Gailly	Ghent University	0
Fredrik Milani	University of Tartu	0
Frieder Ganz	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
G. E. Hoogenboom	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
G. Ripa	CEFRIEL	1
Gaargi Banerjee Dasgupta	IBM Research India	1
Gabriel M. Veiga	Technical University of Lisbon	0

Gabriela Vulcu	National University of Ireland	0
Gabriele Costa	University of Genoa	0
Gabriele Gianini	Etisalat British Telecom Innovation Center (EBTIC)	2
Gal Shachor	IBM Research Israel	1
Galina Deeva	KU Leuven	1
Gang Zhou	Beihang University	0
Gaston Tagni	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Geert Poels	Ghent University	0
Geert Poels	Universiteit Gent	0
Geetika T. Lakshmanan	Audible, Inc.	2
Geetika T. Lakshmanan	IBM Research United States	1
Gema García-Sáez	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	0
Gema Ibanez-Sanchez	Universitat Politècnica de València	0
Geoff Hall	University of Leeds	0
Georg Grossmann	University of South Australia	0
George Koliadis	University of Wollongong	0
George M. Wyner	Boston University School of Management	0
George S. Avrunin	University of Massachusetts	0
George Varvaresos	Business Process Mining	3
Geraldo Landre	Computing College, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS)	0
Geraldo Xexéo	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Geraldo Zimbrão	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Gerasimos Markatos	University of Piraeus	0
Gerd Wagner	Brandenburg Technical University at Cottbus	0
Gerhard Zucker	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology	1
Gero Decker	University of Potsdam	0
Gerrit Tamm	SRH Berlin University of Applied Sciences	0
Gert Janssenswillen	Hasselt University	0
Gertruud A. M. Krekels	Catharina Hospital Eindhoven	3
Getachew Hailemariam	Ababa University	0
Ghalia Tello	Khalifa University of Science and Technology	0
Giampaolo Armellin	Centro Ricerche GPI srl	1

Gian Pietro Picco	University of Trento	0
Giancarlo Guizzardi	Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo	0
Gianluigi Greco	University of Calabria	0
Gianmario Motta	Politecnico di Milano	0
Gideon Magala	KU Leuven	1
Giorgio Bruno	Politecnico di Torino	0
Giovanna Petrone	University of Torino	0
Giovanni Meroni	Politecnico di Milano	0
Giovanni Stilo	Tor Vergata University of Rome	0
Giray Havur	Siemens AG Österreich, Corporate Technology	2
Giray Havur	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Gisela Granitzer	Know-Center Graz	1
Giulio Petrucci	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	1
Giuseppe Berio	University of Torino	0
Giuseppe De Giacomo	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Giuseppe Visaggio	University of Bari	0
Gjergji Kasneci	University of Potsdam	0
Gonzalo Fagalde	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Gordon Blair	Lancaster University	0
Gottfried Vossen	University of Münster	0
Graham Crossmarie	EBM WebSourcing	2
Gregor Engels	University of Paderborn	0
Gregor Engels	Paderborn University	0
Gregor Grambow	Aalen University	0
Gregor Scheithauer	OPITZ CONSULTING GmbH	2
Gregoris Mentzas	National Technical University of Athens	0
Grzegorz J. Nalepa	AGH University of Science and Technology	0
Gu van Rhijn	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research	1
Guang-Jie Ren	IBM Research United States	1
Guido Governatori	CSIRO	1
Guido Governatori	Queensland University of Technology	0
Guido Governatori	National ICT Australia	1
Guillaume Rosinosky	Bonitasoft	2

Guillermo Bustos	Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Valparaiso	0
Gunnar John Coll	Computas AS	2
Guobin Zhu	Wuhan University	0
Guotong Xie	IBM Research China	1
Gustaf Neumann	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Gustavo Pizarro	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Guy Redding	Queensland University of Technology	0
Göran Goldkuhl	Linköping University	0
Günter Karjoth	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Günter Wallner	University of Applied Arts Vienna	0
Hagen Overdick	University of Potsdam	0
Hagen Völzer	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Haifeng Liu	IBM Research China	1
Haiping Zha	Tsinghua University	0
Haiyang Sun	Macquarie University	0
Hajo A. Reijers	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Hajo A. Reijers	University of Utrecht	0
Hajo A. Reijers	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Hajo A. Reijers	Eindhoven University	0
Hajo A. Reijers	Queensland University of Technology	0
Hamid Reza Motahari-Nezhad	IBM Research United States	1
Hamid Reza Motahari-Nezhad	Hewlett Packard Labs	1
Han van der Aa	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Han van der Aa	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Han van der Aa	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Hani Jamjoom	IBM Research United States	1
Hanns-Alexander Dietrich	WWU Muenster - ERCIS	1
Hans Friedrich Witschel	SAP Germany	2
Hans Friedrich Witschel	University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW)	0
Hans-Arno Jacobsen	University of Toronto	0
Hans-Einar Lundli	Trondheim Kommune	3
Hans-Georg Fill	University of Vienna	0
Hans-Jürgen Appelrath	University of Oldenburg	0
Hans-Peter Steiert	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Harald Gall	University of Zurich	0

Harald Kittler	Medical University of Vienna	0
Harald Meyer	University of Potsdam	0
Harald Meyer	Hasso-Plattner-Institute	1
Harald Psailer	Vienna University of Technology	0
Harshavardhan Jegadeesan	SAP Germany	2
Hartwig Baumgärtel	University of Applied Sciences Ulm	0
Haruhisa Takahashi	University of Electro-Communications	0
Hassan Fatemi	University of Twente	0
He Zhang	National ICT Australia	1
Heidi Romero	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Heiko Beck	University of Potsdam	0
Heiko Kern	University of Leipzig	0
Heiko Ludwig	IBM Research United States	1
Heiko Woith	GeoForschungsZentrum Potsdam,	1
Heiner Stuckenschmidt	University of Mannheim	0
Hejiao Huang	Harbin Institute of Technology Shenzhen Graduate School	0
Helen Schonenberg	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Helle Frisak Sem	Computas AS	2
Hema Meda	Tata Consultancy Services	2
Henricus M. W. Verbeek	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Henrik Leopold	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Henrik Leopold	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Henrik Leopold	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Hernan Ponce-de-León	Aalto University	0
Hervé Panetto	University Henri Poincaré (Nancy 1)	0
Hicham Reguieg	Blaise Pascal University	0
Hoa Khanh Dam	University of Wollongong	0
Holger Flemig	itCampus GmbH	2
Holger Meyer	University of Rostock	0
Holger Ziekow	AGT Germany	2
Holger Ziekow	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Hong-Linh Truong	Vienna University of Technology	0
Hongwei Du	Harbin Institute of Technology Shenzhen Graduate School	0

Horst Pichler	University of Klagenfurt	0
Hossein Siadat	Politecnico di Milano	0
Hua Wang	University of Southern Queensland	0
Hua Yan	College of Computing	0
Huayu Zhang	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Hugo Ordóñez	Universidad San Buenaventura	0
Hugo Seguel Pérez	Excellentia BPM	2
Humberto S. García Caballero	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Huy Tran	University of Vienna	0
Huy Tran	Vienna University of Technology	0
Hye-young Paik	The University of New South Wales	0
Hyerim Bae	Pusan National University	0
Hyung Gi Song	Netville Co., Ltd.	2
Hércules S. S. José	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
I. A. Lomazova	National Research University Higher School of Economics	0
I. Guven Arkilic	Precedence B.V.	2
Iain D. Stalker	University of Teesside	0
Ichiro Satoh	National Institute of Informatics	1
Iezalde F. Lopes	University of Lisbon	0
Ignacio García-Rodríguez de Guzmán	University of Castilla-La Mancha	0
Ignacio Silva-Lepe	IBM Research United States	1
Ignacio Terrizzano	IBM Research United States	1
Igor Hawryszkiewicz	University of Technology	0
Il-Jae Wang	Pusan National University Hospital	0
Ilia Bider	Stockholm University	0
Ilona Reischl	AGES PharmMed	3
Ilya Verenich	Queensland University of Technology	0
Iman M. A. Helal	Cairo University	0
Imed Kacem	University Paul Verlaine Metz	0
Imen Azaiz	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	0
Imen Nouira	UMR G-SCOP	1
Imran Sarwar Bajwa	The Islamia University of Bahawalpur	0
Ina Siebert	Harz University of Applied Sciences	0
Inam Soomro	University of Tartu	0
Inge van de Weerd	University of Utrecht	0
Inger Dybdahl Sørby	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0

Ingo Weber	CSIRO	1
Ingo Weber	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Ingo Weber	National ICT Australia	1
Ingo Weber	Software Systems Research Group, NICTA	1
Ingo Weber	SAP Germany	2
Ioannis Patiniotakis	National Technical University of Athens	0
Ioannis Routis	Harokopio University of Athens	0
Irene Barba	University of Seville	0
Irene M. Schönreiter	Technical University Dresden	0
Irene T. P. Vandekeeste	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Irene Teinema	University of Tartu	0
Irfan ul Haq	University of Vienna	0
Iria Estevez-Ayres	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid	0
Irina Ailenei	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Irina Rychkova	Panthéon-Sorbonne University (Paris I)	0
Iris Beerepoot	ICTZ B.V.	2
Iris Reinhartz-Berger	University of Haifa	0
Isabelle Hang	SAP Germany	2
Isao Kojima	Grid Technology Research Center	1
Ismael Caballero	University of Castilla-La Mancha	0
Itana Maria de Souza Gimenes	University of Maringá	0
Ivan Krofak	CES Clean Energy Solutions	2
Ivan Markovic	SAP Germany	2
Ivanna Lazarte	Universidad Tecnológica Nacional	0
Ivor Spence	Queen's University Belfast	0
Iñaki Peña	European Software Institute (ESI)	1
J. Gert-Jan de Vries	Philips Research	1
J. J. C. L. Vogel	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
J. J. Collins	University of Limerick	0
J. Vogel	SAP Research Switzerland	1
Jaco van de Pol	University of Twente	0
Jacopo Lenkiewicz	Gemelli University Hospital	0
Jacques Fleuriot	University of Edinburgh	0
Jacques Wainer	State University of Campinas	0
Jae-Yoon Jung	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Jae-Yoon Jung	Kyung Hee University	0

Jakob Pinggera	University of Innsbruck	0
James Caverlee	College of Computing	0
Jan Brunnert	Hasso-Plattner-Institute	1
Jan Claes	Ghent University	0
Jan Ladleif	University of Potsdam	0
Jan Martijn E. M. van der Werf	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Jan Martijn E. M. van der Werf	University of Utrecht	0
Jan Mendling	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Jan Mendling	Queensland University of Technology	0
Jan Mendling	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Jan Pretzel	GECKO mbH	2
Jan Recker	Queensland University of Technology	0
Jan Recker	SAP Research Australia	1
Jan Ricken	University of Namur	0
Jan van der Wal	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Jan van Moll	Philips Research	1
Jan Vanthienen	KU Leuven	1
Jan vom Brocke	Liechtenstein University	0
Jan-Christian Kuhr	GECKO mbH	2
Jana Koehler	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Jana Koehler	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Jana Prodanova	University of Burgos	0
Jana-Rebecca Rehse	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Janaina F. Marchesi	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Jandisson Soares de Jesus	Universidade de São Paulo	0
Janette Wong	IBM Research Canada	1
Janina Kettenbohrer	University of Bamberg	0
Janne Barnes	Queensland University of Technology	0
Jannis Rake	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Jano Moreira de Souza	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Jason Cohen	University of the Witwatersrand	0
Jason Crampton	University of London	0
Jason Watson	Queensland University of Technology	0
Javier De San Pedro	Technical University of Catalonia	0

Javier Fabra	University of Zaragoza	0
Jean-Guy Schneider	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Jean-Pierre Lorré	EBM WebSourcing	2
Jean-René Coffi	Thales Research and Technology	1
Jeannette Stark	Technical University Dresden	0
Jeff Kramer	Imperial College London	0
Jennifer Hamm	University of Applied Sciences Würzburg-Schweinfurt	0
Jens Drawehn	Fraunhofer Institut für Arbeitswissenschaft und Organisation	1
Jens Gulden	University of Siegen	0
Jens Gulden	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Jens Kolb	Ulm University	0
Jens Lemcke	SAP Germany	2
Jens Werner	Brandenburg Technical University at Cottbus	0
Jeremy Gibson	Queensland University of Technology	0
Jeroen Bolle	Ghent University	0
Jeroen Geerdink	Hospital Group Twente (ZGT)	3
Jesus Mandingorra	Hospital General de Valencia	3
Jiacun Wang	Monmouth University	0
Jiafei Li	Jilin University	0
Jiajie Xu	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Jian Yang	Macquarie University	0
JianJun Yu	Beihang University	0
Jianmin Wang	Tsinghua University	0
Jianrui Wang	The Pennsylvania State University	0
Jianwen Su	University of California at Santa Barbara	0
Jim Sinur	Gartner	2
Jiming Liu	Hong Kong Baptist University	0
Jin Ho Kim	Seoul National University	0
Jing Mei	IBM Research China	1
Jing Tang	Tokyo Institute of Technology	1
Jing Yang	Sun Yat-sen University	0
Jingxin Xu	Queensland University of Technology	0
Jinjun Chen	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Jinli Cao	La Trobe University	0
Jintae Lee	University of Colorado	0
Jo Swinnen	Hasselt University	0
Joachim Herbst	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Joachim Melcher	University of Karlsruhe	0

Joachim Van den Bergh	Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School	0
Joanne Manhães Netto	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Joaquín Ezpeleta	University of Zaragoza	0
Jochen De Weerd	KU Leuven	1
Jochen De Weerd	Queensland University of Technology	0
Jochen Küster	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Joel Ribeiro	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Joel Ribeiro	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Joerg Evermann	Memorial University of Newfoundland	0
Joerg Hofstetter	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Joerg Klueckmann	IDS Scheer AG	2
Joey Kendall-Morwick	Indiana University	0
Johann Eder	University of Klagenfurt	0
Johann Eder	University of Vienna	0
Johannes De Smedt	KU Leuven	1
Johannes De Smedt	University of Edinburgh	0
Johannes De Smedt	University of Edinburgh Business School	0
Johannes M. Schleicher	Vienna University of Technology	0
Johannes Schmitz-Lenders	parcs IT-Consulting GmbH	2
Johannes Seyfried	University of Bayreuth	0
Johannes Tenschert	Friedrich-Alexander University Nürnberg	0
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John Fox	University of Oxford	0
John Hoogland	Pallas Athena	2
John Krogstie	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
John Marberg	IBM Research Israel	1
John Mylopoulos	University of Toronto	0
John Shepherd	The University of New South Wales	0
John Vergo	IBM Research United States	1
Johny Ghattas	University of Haifa	0
Jon Atle Gulla	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0

Jon Espen Ingvaldsen	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
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Jonas Hanot	KU Leuven	1
Jonas Mander-scheid	University of Augsburg	0
Jonas Szalanczi	University of Bayreuth	0
Jonathan Cook	New Mexico State University	0
Jonathan Edel-man	Stanford University	0
Jonghun Park	Seoul National University	0
Jonghyeon Ko	Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology	1
Jonice de O. Sampaio	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Jonnro Erasmus	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Joonsoo Bae	Chonbuk National University	0
Joos C. A. M. Buijs	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Jordi Cortadella	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Jorge Cardoso	University of Madeira	0
Jorge Cardoso	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Jorge L. C. Sanz	IBM Research United States	1
Jorge Muñoz-Gama	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Jorge Muñoz-Gama	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Jorge Roa	Universidad Tecnológica Naciona	0
Jorge Villalobos	Universidad de los Andes	0
Jose Angel Bañares	University of Zaragoza	0
Josef Küng	Johannes Kepler University Linz	0
Josep Carmona	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Josep Sànchez-Ferreres	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Joseph Davis	The University of Sydney	0
Joseph Kramer	IBM Research United States	1
Joseph Yuen	Commonwealth Bank of Australia	2
Josue Obregon	Kyung Hee University	0
José A. Rodrigues Nt.	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
José Antonio Heredia Álvaro	Universitat Jaume I	0

José Borbinha	University of Lisbon	0
José Luiz Fiadeiro	University of Leicester	0
José Miguel Pérez-Álvarez	University of Seville	0
Jovan Stevovic	University of Trento	0
Joyce Nakatumba	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
João Cardoso	University of Lisbon	0
João Carlos de A. R. Gonçalves	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
João E. Ferreira	University of São Paulo	0
João Freitas	KU Leuven	1
João Paulo Almeida	Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo	0
Juan Carlos Corrales	University of Cauca	0
Juan Li	Chinese Academy of Sciences	0
Juan Pulgar	Universidad de Chile	0
Juan Salas-Morales	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
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Jugurta Lisboa-Filho	Universidade Federal de Viçosa	0
Juhnyoung Lee	IBM Research United States	1
Julian Eckert	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Julian Schmitt	University of Rostock	0
Juliana Baptista dos Santos França	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Juliane Dehnert	Fraunhofer-Institut für Software- und Systemtechnik	1
Juliane Siegeris	Fraunhofer-Institut für Software- und Systemtechnik	1
Juliane Siegeris	HTW Berlin University of Applied Sciences	0
Juliane Siegeris	Gematik, Gesellschaft für Telematikanwendungen der Gesundheitskarte mbH	2
Julie Chauvet	UMR LIMOS	1
Julien Vayssière	SAP Research Australia	1
Julius Köpke	University of California at Santa Barbara	0
Jun Han	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Jun Ma	FZI Research Center for Information Technologies	1
Jun Shen	University of Wollongong	0
Jun Shen	Centre for Information Systems and Technology Research School of Information Systems and Technology	0

Junhua Zhang	Shandong University	0
Junichi Iijima	Tokyo Institute of Technology	1
Jurgen Willems	Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School	0
Jussi Vanhatalo	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Justinas Janulevicius	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University	0
Jutta Mülle	University of Karlsruhe	0
Jutta Mülle	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Jyoti M. Bhat	Indian Institute of Management	1
Jörg Becker	University of Münster	0
Jörg Becker	European Research Center for Information Systems	1
Jörg Becker	WWU Muenster - ERCIS	1
Jörg Desel	Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt	0
Jörg Desel	FernUniversität in Hagen	0
Jörg Hoffmann	SAP Germany	2
Jörg Nitzsche	University of Stuttgart	0
Jörg P. Müller	Clausthal University of Technology	0
Jörg Schlundt	PRODATO Integration Technology GmbH	2
Jörg Wurzer	iQser AG	2
Jörg Zwicker	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Jørgen Villadsen	Technical University of Denmark	0
Júlio Campos	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Jürgen Mangler	University of Vienna	0
Jürgen Moormann	Frankfurt School of Finance & Management	0
Jürgen Walter	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
K. Gani	Blaise Pascal University	0
Kaarel Tark	Nortal AS	2
Kai Waelti	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Kais Klai	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Kais Klai	Université Paris 13 Nord (Paris XIII)	0
Kam Hay Fung	The University of New South Wales	0
Kamal Bhattacharya	IBM Research United States	1
Kamel Barkaoui	Center for Studies and Research in Computer Science and Communication	1
Kamel Barkaoui	National Conservatory of Arts and Crafts	0
Kamel Boukhelfa	Mentouri University of Constantine	0
Kamyar Sarshar	Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz	0
Kangchan Lee	Electronics & Telecommunication Research Institute	1

Kangsun Lee	Myongji University	0
Kanika Goel	Queensland University of Technology	0
Karen Marie Lyng	University of Copenhagen	0
Kari Smolander	Lappeenranta University of Technology	0
Karl Aberer	EPF Lausanne	0
Karsten Helbig	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg	0
Karsten Kilian	University of Applied Sciences Würzburg-Schweinfurt	0
Karsten Ploesser	SAP Research Australia	1
Karsten Schmidt	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Karsten Wolf	University of Rostock	0
Karthikeyan Ponnalagu	IBM Research India	1
Karthikeyan Ponnalagu	Robert Bosch	2
Katarina Stanoevska-Slabeva	University of St. Gallen	0
Kate Revoredo	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Katharina Kaiser	Vienna University of Technology	0
Katharina Reiter	University of Innsbruck	0
Katharina Stelzl	University of Bayreuth	0
Kathrin Figl	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Kathrin Kaschner	University of Rostock	0
Kathrin Kirchner	University Hospital Jena	0
Kathrin Kirchner	Berlin School of Economics and Law	0
Kay Römer	University of Lübeck	0
Kayo Iizuka	Senshu University	0
Kazuo Misue	University of Tsukuba	0
Kees Kaan	Gyata BPI Consultants	2
Kees M. van Hee	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Keijo Heljanko	Aalto University	0
Keith D. Swenson	Fujitsu America Inc.	2
Keith Miller	St. Francis Xavier University	0
Kelly Dempski	Accenture Technology Labs	1
Kenneth Nagin	IBM Research Israel	1
Kenneth Wang	Queensland University of Technology	0
Kerwin Jorbina	University of Tartu	0
Kevin Göser	Ulm University	0
Kevin McCormack	DRK Research Institute	1
Khaled Gaaloul	UMR LORIA	1
Khaled Hassine	FSG	0

Khurram Shahzad	Stockholm University	0
Kieran Zucker	University of Leeds	0
Kimon Batoulis	University of Potsdam	0
Kioumars Namiri	SAP Germany	2
Kirsten Vallmuur	Queensland University of Technology	0
Klaus Haller	Swisscom IT Services Finance	2
Klaus Kogler	CES Clean Energy Solutions	2
Klaus Tochtermann	Graz University of Technology	0
Klaus Turowski	University of Augsburg	0
Klemens Böhm	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Knut Hinkelmann	University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW)	0
Koen Daenen	Nokia Bell Labs	1
Koen Vanhoof	Hasselt University	0
Kojiro Nakayama	Systems Development Laboratory, Hitachi Ltd. Ozenji	1
Koki Kato	Fujitsu Ltd.	2
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Konrad Pfadenhauer	Vienna University of Technology	0
Konrad Wieland	Vienna University of Technology	0
Konstantin Ivanov	IDS Scheer AG	2
Kostas Traganos	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Kris Van de Cappelle	KBC Bank & Insurance	2
Kris Verlaenen	KU Leuven	1
Krishnendu Kunti	Infosys Technologies Ltd	2
Kristian Bisgaard Lassen	University of Aarhus	0
Kristof Böhmer	University of Vienna	0
Krzysztof Kaczor	AGH University of Science and Technology	0
Krzysztof Kluza	AGH University of Science and Technology	0
Ksenia Ryndina	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Ksenia Wahler	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Kurt E. Madsen	MetaTech, Inc.	2
Kwang-Hoon Kim	Kyonggi University	0
Kyuhyup Oh	Kyung Hee University	0
Kyuri Kim	Kyung Hee University	0
L. Akroun	Blaise Pascal University	0
L. Bouallouche-Medjkoune	University of Bejaia	0

L. G. Pee	Tokyo Institute of Technology	1
L. Nourine	Blaise Pascal University	0
Lachlan Aldred	Queensland University of Technology	0
Lalit Wangikar	CKM Advisors	2
Lam-Son Lê	University of Wollongong	0
Lamine Aouad	University of Limerick	0
Lara Pietzsch	University of Applied Sciences Würzburg-Schweinfurt	0
Lars Ackermann	University of Bayreuth	0
Laura C. Anderson	IBM Research United States	1
Laurent Bagnoud	University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland	0
Laurent Henocque	Laboratoire des sciences de l'information et des systèmes	1
Lav R. Varshney	IBM Research United States	1
Lavanya Ramakrishnan	Lawrence Berkeley National Lab	1
Lazhar Hamel	High School of Computer Science and Mathematics	0
Le-Hung Vu	EPF Lausanne	0
Lea Kutvonen	University of Helsinki	0
Lea Rupprecht	University of Augsburg	0
Leandro Nahabedian	Universidad de Buenos Aires	0
Leen Jooke	Hasselt University	0
Lei Huang	Beijing Jiaotong University	0
Leila Karich	University of Applied Sciences Würzburg-Schweinfurt	0
Leon J. Osterweil	University of Massachusetts	0
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Leonard Nürnberg	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Leonardo S. L. Bastos	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Leslie Shing	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	1
Lesly Devadder	KU Leuven	1
Leticia Duboc	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Li Yan	Huawei Technologies	2
Lih Raichelson	University of Haifa	0
Lijie Wen	Tsinghua University	0
Liliana Ardissono	University of Torino	0
Liljana Stojanovic	University of Karlsruhe	0
Liming Zhu	National ICT Australia	1
Ling Liu	College of Computing	0

Linh Duy Pham	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Linh Thao Ly	Ulm University	0
Lior Limonad	IBM Research Israel	1
Liqiang Geng	National Research Council Canada, Fredericton	1
Lisa F. Seymour	University of Cape Town	0
Lisa Grumbach	University of Trier	0
Lisa Luise Mannel	RWTH Aachen University	0
Liu Yingbo	Tsinghua University	0
Lizhen Cui	Shandong University	0
Liziane Santos Soares	Universidade Federal de Viçosa	0
Lluís Padró	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Lois M. L. Delcambre	Portland State University	0
Lorenzo Gallucci	Exeura s.r.l	2
Lorenzo Rossi	University of Camerino	0
Lori A. Clarke	University of Massachusetts	0
Lotfi Bouzguenda	University Toulouse 1 (Toulouse 1)	0
Lothar Thiele	ETH	0
Luca Console	University of Torino	0
Luca Mottola	Swedish Institute of Computer Science	1
Luca Viganò	King's College London	0
Lucas Francisco da Matta Vegi	Universidade Federal de Viçosa	0
Lucas O. Meertens	University of Twente	0
Lucia Aparici-Tortajada	Universitat Politècnica de València	0
Lucia Sacchi	University of Pavia	0
Luciano Baresi	Politecnico di Milano	0
Luciano García-Bañuelos	Universidad Autónoma de Tlaxcala	0
Luciano García-Bañuelos	University of Tartu	0
Luciano Serafini	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	1
Lucineia Heloisa Thom	Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul	0
Lucineia Heloisa Thom	Université Joseph Fourier (Grenoble 1)	0
Ludwig Stage	University of Groningen	0
Ludwig Zellner	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München	0
Luigi Pontieri	CNR ICAR	1
Luis Marco-Ruiz	University Hospital of North Norway	0
Luis Merchan	Universidad San Buenaventura	0

Luisa Parody	Universidad Loyola Andalucía	0
Luisa Parody	University of Seville	0
Luise Pufahl	University of Potsdam	0
Luiz Paulo Carvalho	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Luís Ferreira Pires	University of Twente	0
M. Bouet	Blaise Pascal University	0
M. F. Sani	RWTH Aachen University	0
M. J. Stegeman	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
M. Junghans	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
M. Moser	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
M. Radzinski	ATOS Research	1
M. Schneider	Blaise Pascal University	0
M. W. N. C. Loosschilder	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Ma Carmen Penadés	Technical University of Valencia	0
Maarten Leurs	Delloitte	2
Maarten Oestreich	University of Potsdam	0
Madhushi Bandara	The University of New South Wales	0
Mahdi Ghasemi	University of Ottawa	0
Maher Rebai	University of Technology of Troyes	0
Mahmoud Boufaida	Mentouri University of Constantine	0
Maikel L. van Eck	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Maja Pesic	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Majed Alshammari	University of Oxford	0
Majid Rafiei	RWTH Aachen University	0
Malika Ioualalen	University Of Science And Technology Houari Boumediene	0
Malu Castellanos	Hewlett Packard Labs	1
Manfred Grauer	University of Siegen	0
Manfred Hauswirth	EPF Lausanne	0
Manfred Reichert	University of Twente	0
Manfred Reichert	Ulm University	0
Mangala Gowri Nanda	IBM Research India	1
Manu De Backer	Ghent University	0
Manu De Backer	KU Leuven	1

Manuel Camargo	University of Tartu	0
Manuel Gall	University of Vienna	0
Manuel Goetz	University of Bayreuth	0
Manuel Lama	University of Santiago de Compostela	0
Manuel Mucientes	University of Santiago de Compostela	0
Manuel Neurauter	University of Innsbruck	0
Manuel Pastrana	Universidad San Buenaventura	0
Manuel Resinas Arias de Reyna	University of Seville	0
Manuel Wimmer	Vienna University of Technology	0
Maolin Pan	Sun Yat-sen University	0
Mar Marcos	Universitat Jaume I	0
Mara Nikolaidou	Harokopio University of Athens	0
Marc Häbich	IBM Research Germany	1
Marc Solé	CA Strategic Research, CA Technologies	1
Marc Verdonk	Delloitte	2
Marc Voorhoeve	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Marcel Walter	University of Münster	0
Marcello La Rosa	The University of Melbourne	0
Marcello La Rosa	Queensland University of Technology	0
Marcello La Rosa	National ICT Australia	1
Marcello La Rosa	Politecnico di Torino	0
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Marcelo Bronzo Ladeira	Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	0
Marcelo Cataldo	Carnegie Mellon University	0
Marcelo Fantinato	State University of Campinas	0
Marcia Stockton	IBM Research United States	1
Marcin Hewelt	University of Potsdam	0
Marco A. A. Vaz	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Marco A. Buseti	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Marco Brambilla	Politecnico di Milano	0
Marco Camer- anesi	Marche Polytechnic University	0
Marco Comuzzi	Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology	1
Marco Comuzzi	Politecnico di Milano	0
Marco Furtner	University of Innsbruck	0
Marco Grasso	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Marco Link	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Marco Montali	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Marco Montali	University of Bologna	0
Marco P. Locatelli	University of Milano-Bicocca	0
Marco Pegoraro	RWTH Aachen University	0

Marco Ronchetti	University of Trento	0
Marco Rospoche	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	1
Marco Santorum	Grenoble University	0
Marco Zapletal	Vienna University of Technology	0
Marcos Paulo Valadares De Oliveira	Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo	0
Marcos R. S. Borges	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Marcos Sepúlveda	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Marcus Dees	Uitvoeringsinstituut Werknemersverzekeringen (UWV)	1
Marcus Fischer	University of Würzburg	0
Mari Abe	IBM Research Japan	1
Maria Beatriz Felgar de Toledo	State University of Campinas	0
Maria Bergholtz	Stockholm University	0
Maria Grazia Fugini	Politecnico di Milano	0
Maria Istela Cagnin	Computing College, Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul (UFMS)	0
Maria Leitner	University of Vienna	0
Maria Orlowska	Queensland University of Technology	0
Maria Ribera Sancho	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Maria-Eugenia Iacob	University of Twente	0
Marian Benner-Wickner	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Marian Lux	University of Vienna	0
Marie Koorneef	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Marie-Aude Au-faure	École Centrale Paris	0
Marie-Christine Fauvet	Grenoble University	0
Marie-Sophie Denner	University of Bayreuth	0
Marielba Zacarias	Universidade do Algarve	0
Marino Segnan	University of Torino	0
Mario Piattini	University of Castilla-La Mancha	0
Mario Sánchez	Universidad de los Andes	0
Mariska Netjes	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Marisol Garcia-Valls	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid	0

Mark Elcock	Retrieval Services Queensland (RSQ)	3
Mark Hoogendoorn	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Mark Linehan	IBM Research United States	1
Mark Staples	National ICT Australia	1
Mark Strembeck	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Markku Hinkka	Aalto University	0
Marko Vujasinovic	Breza Software Engineering Company	2
Markus Bandt	University of Rostock	0
Markus Hammori	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Markus Hipp	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Markus Kohlbacher	Campus 02 University of Applied Sciences	0
Markus Kress	University of Karlsruhe	0
Markus Lauer	Ulm University	0
Markus Linden	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Markus Martini	University of Innsbruck	0
Markus Nüttgens	University of Hamburg	0
Markus Reiter	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Markus Schaefermeyer	University of Frankfurt	0
Markus Stumptner	University of South Australia	0
Marlon Dumas	Queensland University of Technology	0
Marlon Dumas	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Marlon Dumas	University of Tartu	0
Marta Cimitile	Unitelma Sapienza University	0
Marta Indulska	Queensland University of Technology	0
Marten van Sinderen	University of Twente	0
Martin Atzmueller	Tilburg University	0
Martin Bauer	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Martin Berner	University of Mannheim	0
Martin Böhringer	Chemnitz University of Technology	0
Martin Jurisch	Ulm University	0
Martin Jurisch	AristaFlow GmbH	2
Martin Jähne	Fraunhofer-Institut für Intelligente Analyse- und Informationssysteme IAIS	1
Martin Lehnert	University of Augsburg	0
Martin Matzner	University of Münster	0
Martin McCreesh	Iontas/Verint	2

Martin R. Carpenter	University of Manchester	0
Martin Roth	University of Leipzig	0
Martin Schultz	University of Applied Sciences Wedel	0
Marwane El Kharbili	IDS Scheer AG	2
Maryam Razavian	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Marzieh Bakhshandeh	University of Lisbon	0
Marzougui Borhen	Emirates College of Technology	0
María Adela Grando	University of Edinburgh	0
María Adela Grando	University of California at San Diego	0
María Agustina Cibrán	Thales Research and Technology	1
María Cecilia Bastarrica	Universidad de Chile	0
María Laura Caliusco	Universidad Tecnológica Nacional	0
María Teresa Gómez-López	University of Seville	0
Massimiliano de Leoni	University of Padova	0
Massimiliano de Leoni	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Massimiliano de Leoni	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Massimo Mecella	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Massimo Ruffolo	Exeura s.r.l	2
Mateusz Ślażyński	AGH University of Science and Technology	0
Matheus Hauder	Technische Universität München	0
Mathias Fritzsche	SAP Research United Kingdom	1
Mathias Kleiner	ILOG	2
Mathias Niepert	University of Mannheim	0
Mathias Weske	University of Potsdam	0
Mathias Weske	Hasso-Plattner-Institute	1
Mathieu Braem	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	0
Mathijs Creemers	Hasselt University	0
Mathilde Boltenhagen	Université Paris-Saclay	0
Mati Golani	Technion-Israel Institute of Technology	1

Mati Golani	Ort Braude College	0
Matteo Baldoni	University of Torino	0
Matteo Magnani	University of Bologna	0
Matteo Zavatteri	University of Verona	0
Matthew Duftler	IBM Research United States	1
Matthias Book	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Matthias Book	University of Iceland	0
Matthias Born	SAP Germany	2
Matthias Kunze	University of Potsdam	0
Matthias Perktold	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Matthias Steinhorst	WWU Muenster - ERCIS	1
Matthias Weidlich	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Matthias Weidlich	Imperial College London	0
Matthias Weidlich	University of Potsdam	0
Matthias Weidlich	Technion-Israel Institute of Technology	1
Matthias Wieland	University of Stuttgart	0
Maurice van Keulen	University of Twente	0
Maurizio Castellano	Università degli Studi di Brescia	0
Maurizio Marchese	University of Trento	0
Maurizio Sebastianis	Think3 Inc.	2
Maurizio Talamo	Tor Vergata University of Rome	0
Mauro Gambini	University of Verona	0
Mauro Vallati	University of Huddersfield	0
Max Mühlhäuser	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Maxim Dochez	KU Leuven	1
Maxime Fonda	Qualnet	2
Maximilian Röglinger	University of Bayreuth	0
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Maya Barnea	IBM Research Israel	1
Maya Kaner	Ort Braude College	0
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Maya Lincoln	Israel Institute of Technology	1

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Meike Ullrich	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
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Melanie Polderdijk	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Melanie Siebenhaar	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Melissa Buco	IBM Research United States	1
Meng Wang	China Mobile Communications Corporation	2
Merih Seran Uysal	RWTH Aachen University	0
Mi Pan	Zhejiang University	0
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Michael Arias	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Michael Backmann	University of Potsdam	0
Michael Becker	AUDI AG	2
Michael Becker	University of Leipzig	0
Michael Genrich	Fujitsu Consulting Limited	2
Michael Granitzer	Know-Center Graz	1
Michael Herrmann	DaimlerChrysler AG	2
Michael Huth	Imperial College London	0
Michael Kaiser	University of Innsbruck	0
Michael Kishinevsky	Intel Corporation	2
Michael Leyer	Frankfurt School of Finance & Management	0
Michael Möhring	Hochschule München	0
Michael Möhring	Aalen University	0
Michael Möhring	Hochschule Aalen	0
Michael Niemann	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Michael Picht	SAP Germany	2
Michael Predeschly	Ulm University	0
Michael Prilla	Ruhr University of Bochum	0
Michael Radloff	University of Hamburg	0
Michael Rohloff	University of Potsdam	0
Michael Rosemann	Queensland University of Technology	0
Michael Rosemann	SAP Research Australia	1

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Michael Schrefl	University of South Australia	0
Michael Schrefl	Johannes Kepler University Linz	0
Michael Soanes	University of Technology	0
Michael Stach	Ulm University	0
Michael Stein	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Michael Stoute	Intellipro, Inc.	2
Michael Westergaard	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Michael Zimoch	Ulm University	0
Michael zur Muehlen	Stevens Institute of Technology	1
Michael zur Muehlen	Howe School of Technology Management	0
Michaël Petit	University of Namur	0
Michel A. Westenberg	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Michel Cuendet	University Hospital of Lausanne	0
Michel Gourgand	UMR LIMOS	1
Michele Dassisti	Politecnico di Bari	0
Michele Mancoppi	University of Stuttgart	0
Michele Sebag	Universite Paris Sud (Paris XI)	0
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Michiharu Kudo	IBM Research Japan	1
Michiko Oba	Software Division, Hitachi Ltd.	2
Mieke J. Jans	Hasselt University	0
Miguel Malheiros	INOV	1
Miguel Valdes Faura	Bull R&D	1
Miguel Ángel Corella	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	0
Mikael Lind	University College of Borås	0
Mike A. Marin	IBM Research United States	1
Milan Petković	Philips Research	1
Minhong Wang	The University of Hong Kong	0
Minseok Song	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Minseok Song	Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology	1
Minseok Song	Pohang University of Science and Technology	0
Minsu Cho	Pohang University of Science and Technology	0

Mirel Cosulschi	University at Craiova	0
Mirela Botezatu	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Mirela Riveni	Vienna University of Technology	0
Mirko Sonntag	University of Stuttgart	0
Mitra Herav- izadeh	Queensland University of Technology	0
Moe Thandar Kyaw Wynn	Queensland University of Technology	0
Moez Yeddes	National School of Computer Sciences	0
Mohamed Graiet	High School of Computer Science and Mathematics	0
Mohamed Karim Aroua	University of Tunis El Manar	0
Mohamed Sellami	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Mohamed Tahar Bhiri	MIRACL, ISIMS	1
Mohammad Ehson Rangih	City, University of London	0
Mohammadreza Fani Sani	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Mohsen Rouached	UMR LORIA	1
Moisés Lima Pérez	Independent BPM Author	3
Mokrane Bouzeghoub	Université Paris-Saclay	0
Mona Vajihollahi	Simon Fraser University	0
Monika Gupta	IBM Research India	1
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Monika Kochanowski	Fraunhofer Institut für Arbeitswissenschaft und Organisation	1
Monika Malinova	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Monique H. Jansen-Vullers	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Monique Snoeck	KU Leuven	1
Montserrat Es- tañol	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Mor Peleg	University of Haifa	0
Morten Marquard	Exformatics A/S	2
Moshiur Bhuiyan	University of Wollongong	0
Mouna Makni	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Mourad Amziani	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Mourad Kmimech	MIRACL, ISIMS	1
Mu Qiao	The Pennsylvania State University	0

Muhammad Adnan Tariq	University of Stuttgart	0
Muhammad Ahtisham Aslam	University of Leipzig	0
Muhammad Shahzad	Exformatics A/S	2
Murat Firat	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Murray Spork	SAP Research United States	1
Mustafa Mısır	Universite Paris Sud (Paris XI)	0
Márcio K. Oikawa	University of São Paulo	0
N. Guerrouahane	University of Bejaia	0
N. Ilker Altintas	Cybersoft Information Technologies	2
Nacer Boudjlida	University Henri Poincaré (Nancy 1)	0
Nadja Damij	University of Ljubljana	0
Nancy Alexopoulou	University of Athens	0
Nanjangud C. Narendra	Cognizant Technology Solutions	2
Natalia Sidorova	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Nataliya Mulyar	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Naved Ahmed	University of Tartu	0
Nazia Leyla	St. Francis Xavier University	0
Nejib Ben Hadj-Alouane	National Engineering School of Tunis	0
Nenad Stojanovic	FZI Research Center for Information Technologies	1
Nesi Outmazgin	University of Haifa	0
Nicholas Fleury	EBM WebSourcing	2
Nick Fung	University of Twente	0
Nick R. T. P. van Beest	CSIRO	1
Nick R. T. P. van Beest	National ICT Australia	1
Nick Russell	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Nick Russell	Queensland University of Technology	0
Nico Aßfalg	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Nico Herbig	Saarland University	0
Nico Herzberg	University of Potsdam	0
Nicola Costantini	Siav SpA	2
Nicola Guarino	CNR ISTC	1
Nicola Leone	University of Calabria	0
Nicola Zannone	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Nicolai Fischer	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Nicolas Cuntz	University of Siegen	0

Nicolas Mundbrod	Ulm University	0
Nicolas Museux	Thales Research and Technology	1
Nicolas Pflanzl	University of Münster	0
Nicolas Poggi	Technical University of Catalonia	0
Nicole Zeise	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Nicoletta Dessì	University of Cagliari	0
Nicolás D'ippolito	Universidad de Buenos Aires	0
Niels Joncheere	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	0
Niels Lohmann	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Niels Lohmann	University of Rostock	0
Niels Lohmann	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Niels Martin	Hasselt University	0
Nikolaj Goranin	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University	0
Nikolay D. Mehandjiev	University of Manchester	0
Nikos Anerousis	IBM Research United States	1
Nikos Papageorgiou	National Technical University of Athens	0
Nili Guy (Ifergan)	IBM Research Israel	1
Nina Oertel	SAP Germany	2
Ning Bao	Harbin Institute of Technology Shenzhen Graduate School	0
Nirmal K. Mukhi	IBM Research United States	1
Nirmit Desai	IBM Research India	1
Niz Safrudin	Queensland University of Technology	0
Nomane Ould Ahmed M'bareck	Institut National des Télécommunications	1
Norbert Kuhn	Trier University of Applied Sciences	0
Norihisa Komoda	Osaka University	0
Norikazu Matsuyama	PFU Active Labs Limited	1
Noshir Contractor	Northwestern University	0
Nour Assy	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Nour Damer	Hasselt University	0
Nuno Flores	Universidade do Porto	0
Oana Nicolae	Brandenburg Technical University at Cottbus	0
Ognjen Scekcic	Vienna University of Technology	0
Oktay Turetken	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Ole A. Alsos	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
Olena Skarlat	Vienna University of Technology	0
Olga Levina	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Olha Danylevych	University of Stuttgart	0
Oliver Grasl	Transentis management consulting GmbH	2

Oliver Günther	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Oliver Holschke	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Oliver Kopp	University of Stuttgart	0
Oliver Müller	Liechtenstein University	0
Oliver Thomas	Saarland University	0
Olivera Marjanovic	The University of Sydney	0
Olivia Oanea	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Olivier Perrin	UMR LORIA	1
Omar Chiotti	Universidad Tecnológica Naciona	0
Omar Chiotti	INGAR-CONICET	2
Onno Vijlbrief	Hospital Group Twente (ZGT)	3
Onur Demirors	Middle East Technical University	0
Onur Demirors	The University of New South Wales	0
Onur Özkök	Başkent University	0
Orlenys López-Pintado	University of Tartu	0
Ornella Perak	Hof University of Applied Sciences	0
Osama El-Hassan	University of Leicester	0
Oscar González-Rojas	Universidad de los Andes	0
Ourania Hatzi	Harokopio University of Athens	0
Owen A. Johnson	University of Leeds	0
Owen Keates	Queensland University of Technology	0
P. A. M. Kleingeld	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
P. J. M. Bakker	University of Amsterdam	0
Pablo Basanta	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid	0
Pablo Castells	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	0
Pablo David Villarreal	Universidad Tecnológica Naciona	0
Pablo E. Guerrero	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Pablo Rosales	Kyung Hee University	0
Padmanabhan Krishnan	Bond University	0
Pankaj Dhoolia	IBM Research India	1
Pankaj Jalote	Indian Institute of Management	1
Paola Mello	University of Bologna	0
Paolo Baldan	University of Padova	0
Paolo Felli	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Paolo Giorgini	University of Trento	0
Paolo Terenziani	University of Eastern Piedmont	0
Paolo Tonella	Fondazione Bruno Kessler	1
Pascal Poizat	UMR LIP6	1

Patricia Rogetzer	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Patrick Albert	ILOG	2
Patrick Delfmann	University of Münster	0
Patrick Delfmann	WWU Muenster - ERCIS	1
Patrick Driscoll	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
Patrick Lohmann	Stevens Institute of Technology	1
Patrick Lübbecke	Saarland University	0
Patrick Mikalef	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
Patrik Spieß	SAP Germany	2
Paul Alvino	Defence Science and Technology Group	2
Paul Grefen	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Paul Harmon	Business Process Trends	1
Paul Johannesson	Stockholm University	0
Paul Johannesson	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	0
Paul Mathiesen	Queensland University of Technology	0
Paul Pichler	University of Innsbruck	0
Paul T. Keyser	IBM Research United States	1
Pauline Antho- nysamy	Lancaster University	0
Pavel Andreev	University of Ottawa	0
Pavel Kucherbaev	University of Trento	0
Pavlos Delias	Kavala Institute of Technology	1
Pedro C. Diniz	Technical University of Lisbon	0
Pedro C. L. Mon- teiro	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Pedro Ferreira	INOV	1
Pedro García- López	Universitat Rovira i Virgili	0
Pedro Henrique Piccoli Richetti	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Pedro M. Esposito	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Pedro Álvarez	University of Zaragoza	0
Peng Sun	Arizona State University	0
Peter Braun	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Peter Chamoni	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Peter Dadam	Ulm University	0
Peter Fettke	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz	0
Peter Fettke	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intel- ligenz	1
Peter Fettke	Saarland University	0
Peter Gloor	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	1
Peter Green	Queensland University of Technology	0
Peter Heisig	Technical University Dresden	0

Peter K. Schwab	Friedrich-Alexander University Nürnberg	0
Peter Kilpatrick	Queen's University Belfast	0
Peter Loos	Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz	0
Peter Loos	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Peter Loos	Saarland University	0
Peter Massuthe	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Peter Mattheis	Hochschule Furtwangen	0
Peter Trkman	University of Ljubljana	0
Peter van den Brand	Fluxicon	2
Peter van der Molen	Gyata BPI Consultants	2
Peter Willaert	Vlerick Leuven Gent Management School	0
Petia Wohed	KTH Royal Institute of Technology	0
Petia Wohed	University Henri Poincaré (Nancy 1)	0
Petros Papapanagiotou	University of Edinburgh	0
Phil Gilbert	IBM Research United States	1
Philip Effinger	Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen	0
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Philip S. Yu	University of Illinois at Chicago	0
Philipp Hoenisch	Vienna University of Technology	0
Philipp Staudt	Saarland University	0
Philipp Walter	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Philippe Quéinnec	Université de Toulouse	0
Phillipa Oaks	Queensland University of Technology	0
Pierluigi Plebani	Politecnico di Milano	0
Piero Fraternali	Politecnico di Milano	0
Pierre Féliès	UMR LIMOS	1
Pierre Sachse	University of Innsbruck	0
Pieter De Koninck	KU Leuven	1
Pieter Hens	KU Leuven	1
Pieter J. Tousseint	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	0
Pieter Van Gorp	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Pille Pullonen	Cybernetica AS	2
Pin Chen	DSTO	1
Piotr Wiśniewski	AGH University of Science and Technology	0
Pnina Soffer	University of Haifa	0

Ponn Sundhararajan	IBM Research United States	1
Prabhakar M. Dixit	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Prabir Nandi	IBM Research United States	1
Prasad Jayaweera	University of Ruhuna	0
Prerna Juneja	Indraprastha Institute of Information Technology, Delhi (IIITD)	1
Qing Wang	Chinese Academy of Sciences	0
Qinlong Guo	Tsinghua University	0
R. Ceballos	University of Seville	0
R. P. Jagadeesh Chandra Bose	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Rabeb Mizouni	Khalifa University of Science and Technology	0
Rachid Meziani	University of Vincennes in Saint-Denis (Paris VIII)	0
Raf Haesen	KU Leuven	1
Rafael Accorsi	University of Freiburg	0
Rafael Gomes Barradas	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Rafael M. Gasca	University of Seville	0
Raffaella Mirandola	Politecnico di Milano	0
Raffaele Conforti	Queensland University of Technology	0
Raffaele Conforti	The University of Melbourne	0
Raghava Rao Mukkamala	IT University of Copenhagen	0
Ragnhild Van Der Straeten	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	0
Raimundas Matulevičius	University of Tartu	0
Rainer Anzböck	D.A.T.A. Corporation	2
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Rainer Schmidt	Hochschule Aalen	0
Rainer Schmidt	Trier University of Applied Science	0
Rainer Schmidt	Aalen University	0
Raju N. Gottumukkala	Louisiana Tech University	0
Ralf Laue	University of Applied Sciences Zwickau	0
Ralf Laue	University of Leipzig	0
Ralf Steinmetz	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Ralf-Christian Härting	Aalen University	0

Ralf-Christian Härting	Hochschule Aalen	0
Ralph Bergmann	University of Trier	0
Ralph Bobrik	Ulm University	0
Ralph Mietzner	University of Stuttgart	0
Rama Akkiraju	IBM Research United States	1
Rami-Habib Eid-Sabbagh	University of Potsdam	0
Ramzan Talib	University of Bayreuth	0
Ramzi Hammami	Toulouse Business School	0
Ran Chen	Tsinghua University	0
Rania Khalaf	IBM Research United States	1
Rasmus Hjardem-Hansen	Greve Municipality	3
Rehan Syed	Queensland University of Technology	0
Reiko Heckel	University of Leicester	0
Reina Uba	University of Tartu	0
Reinhold Dunkl	University of Vienna	0
Remco Dijkman	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Remzi Solmaz	Cybersoft Information Technologies	2
Renata Mendes de Araujo	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Rene de la Fuente	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Renuka R. Sindhgatta	IBM Research India	1
René Peinl	Hof University of Applied Sciences	0
René Wörzberger	RWTH Aachen University	0
Reuven Karni	ProcessGene Ltd.	2
Reuven Karni	Israel Institute of Technology	1
Reuven Karni	Shenkar College of Engineering and Design	0
Revathi Subramanian	IBM Research United States	1
Reyes Grangel	Universitat Jaume I	0
Ricardo Alfredo Quintano Neira	Pontificia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro	0
Ricardo Chalmeta	Universitat Jaume I	0
Ricardo Fuentes	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Ricardo Lira	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
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Riccardo Cognini	University of Camerino	0

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Richard Müller		University of Leipzig	0
Rik Eshuis		Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Rim Larbi		National Engineering School of Tunis	0
Rob J. B. Vanwersch		Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Robert Andrews		Queensland University of Technology	0
Robert Dunlop		InferMed Ltd	2
Robert Engel		Vienna University of Technology	0
Robert Enyedi		IBM Research United States	1
Robert Gombotz		Vienna University of Technology	0
Robert Heinrich		Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Robert Heinrich		University of Heidelberg	0
Robert Klawes		Deutsche Bank AG	2
Robert Lorenz		Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt	0
Robert Mertens		HSW University of Applied Sciences	0
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Roberto Furnari		University of Torino	0
Roberto Gatta		Universit Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	0
Roberto Gatta		Università degli Studi di Brescia	0
Roberto Guanciale		KTH Royal Institute of Technology	0
Roberto Micalizio		University of Torino	0
Roberto Posenato		University of Verona	0
Roberto Vigo		Siav SpA	2
Robin Bergenthum		FernUniversität in Hagen	0
Robin Bergenthum		Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt	0
Rodrigo Magalhães		INOV	1
Roe Shraga		Technion-Israel Institute of Technology	1
Roel J. Wieringa		University of Twente	0

Roger Tregear	Leonardo Consulting	2
Roland Imoberdorf	UMB AG	2
Roland Stuehmer	University of Karlsruhe	0
Roland Stuehmer	FZI Research Center for Information Technologies	1
Roland Woodtly	Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts	0
Romain Emens	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Roman Brun	University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW)	0
Roman Mühlberger	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Roman Vaculín	IBM Research United States	1
Ronald Brandtjen	ProcessGold AG	2
Ronald E. Giachetti	Florida International University	0
Rong Liu	The Pennsylvania State University	0
Rong Liu	IBM Research United States	1
Rongbin Xu	Anhui University	0
Ronny S. Mans	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Ronny Seiger	Technical University Dresden	0
Roozbeh Farahbod	Simon Fraser University	0
Rosalba Giugno	University of Catania	0
Rosario Curia	Exeura s.r.l	2
Rosemary Francisco	Pontifical Catholic University of Parana	0
Ross Brown	Queensland University of Technology	0
Ross Jeffery	National ICT Australia	1
Ross S. Veitch	University of Cape Town	0
Rouven Poll	University of Augsburg	0
Roy Oberhauser	Aalen University	0
Roy R. H. M. J. Goverde	Precedence B.V.	2
Rubén Mondéjar	Universitat Rovira i Virgili	0
Rudolf Kuhn	ProcessGold AG	2
Rui Henriques	Technical University of Lisbon	0
Rui M. Santos	University of Lisbon	0
Runzhuo Li	University of Ottawa	0
Ruopeng Lu	Queensland University of Technology	0
Russell R. Barton	The Pennsylvania State University	0
Ruth Breu	University of Innsbruck	0
Ryszard Kowalczyk	Swinburne University of Technology	0

Rébecca Deneck- ère	Panthéon-Sorbonne University (Paris I)	0
Régis Riveret	CSIRO	1
Rüdiger Pryss	Ulm University	0
Rüdiger Weißbach	Hamburg University of Applied Sciences	0
S. Abels	TIE	1
S. Blood	TIE	1
S. Bouzouzou	University of Bejaia	0
Sabrina Blaukopf	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Sachin Karadgi	University of Siegen	0
Said Mirza Pahlevi	Grid Technology Research Center	1
Saimir Bala	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Saleem Malik	The Islamia University of Bahawalpur	0
Salvador Trujillo	IK4-Ikerlan Research Center	1
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Sameera Palipana	Aalto University	0
Sami Bhiri	UMR LORIA	1
Sami Bhiri	National University of Ireland	0
Sami Jantunen	Lappeenranta University of Technology	0
Samia Mazhar	Queensland University of Technology	0
Samir Tata	Institut National des Télécommunications	1
Samir Tata	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Samir Youcef	Université de Lorraine	0
Samrend Saboor	University for Health Sciences, Medical Informat- ics and Technology (UMIT)	0
Samson W. Tu	Stanford University	0
Samuel J. Burri	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Samuel Kallner	IBM Research Israel	1
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Sander J. J. Lee- mans	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Sander van Wijk	Delloitte	2
Sandugash Askarova	L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University	0
Sandy Hahn	IBM Research United States	1
Sandy Kemsley	Kemsley Design Ltd.	2
Sang Chan Park	Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technol- ogy	1
Sanjiva Weer- awarana	WSO2	2

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Sanna Malinen	Tampere University of Technology	0
Santiago Gómez Sáez	University of Stuttgart	0
Sanya Uehara	Fujitsu Ltd.	2
Sara Houhou	UMR LIP6	1
Sara Migliorini	University of Verona	0
Sarah Kadish	Dana-Farber Cancer Institute	1
Sari Kujala	Tampere University of Technology	0
Sarra Trabelsi	National Engineering School of Tunis	0
Satish Chikkagoudar	Naval Research Laboratory	1
Saurabh Sinha	IBM Research India	1
Schahram Dustdar	Vienna University of Technology	0
Scott Buffett	National Research Council Canada, Fredericton	1
Scott Schorno	IBM Research United States	1
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Sebastian Frischbier	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
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Sebastian Hinz	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
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Sebastian Wagner	University of Stuttgart	0
Sebastien Truptil	Université de Toulouse	0
Sebastián Uchitel	Universidad de Buenos Aires	0
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Selim Larsch	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1

Selma Limam Mansar	Zayed University	0
Selmin Nurcan	Panthéon-Sorbonne University (Paris I)	0
Selwyn Piramuthu	University of Florida	0
Sema Seyhan	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Semih Cetin	Cybersoft Information Technologies	2
Semra Catalkaya	Ulm University	0
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Seok-Ran Yeom	Pusan National University Hospital	0
Seppe K. L. M. vanden Broucke	KU Leuven	1
Serge Dela-fontaine	HES-SO Valais	0
Sergey Smirnov	University of Potsdam	0
Sergio Storari	University of Ferrara	0
Sergio Tessaris	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Seung-Kyun Han	Seoul National University	0
Seyed Alireza Hajimirsadeghi	The University of New South Wales	0
Seyed Amin Tabatabaei	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	0
Seyed-Mehdi-Reza Beheshti	The University of New South Wales	0
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Shamsul Duha	City, University of London	0
Sharat R. Sabbella	Sharat Industries	2
Shawn Bowers	University of California Davis	0
Shaya Pourmirza	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Shazia Sadiq	Queensland University of Technology	0
Sherif Sakr	The University of New South Wales	0
Sherif Sakr	National ICT Australia	1
Shivali Agarwal	IBM Research India	1
Shivali Agarwal	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Shreeraman Ponpathirkoottam	Saarland University	0
Shreyasi Pathak	University of Twente	0
Shu Tao	IBM Research United States	1
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Sietse Overbeek	Delft University of Technology	0

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Silke Balzert	Saarland University	0
Silvana Castano	University of Milan	0
Silvana Quaglini	University of Pavia	0
Silvano Colombo Tosatto	CSIRO	1
Silvia Lucchini	Politecnico di Milano	0
Silvia Miksch	Vienna University of Technology	0
Silvio Ghilardi	University of Milan	0
Silvio Hamacher	Pontificia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro	0
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Simon Brander	University of Applied Sciences Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW)	0
Simon Malkowski	Georgia Institute of Technology	1
Simon Martin	University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland	0
Simon Moser	IBM Research Germany	1
Simon Razniewski	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Simon Stelzl	University of Augsburg	0
Simon Trillsch	University Hospital of Giessen and Marburg	0
Simon Vogt	Helmut-Schmidt-Universität Hamburg	0
Simon-James Loveland	Trondheim Kommune	3
Simona Rabinovici-Cohen	IBM Research Israel	1
Simone Agostinelli	Sapienza University of Rome	0
Simone Kriglstein	Secure Business Austria	2
Simone van der Geer	Erasmus Medical Center	3
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Sira Yongchareon	Unitec Institute of Technology	1
Sira Yongchareon	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Sivadon Chaisiri	University of Waikato	0
Sivaprashanth Danturthy	IBM Research United States	1
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Sophie Rodier	UMR LIMOS	1

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Srinath Perera	WSO2	2
Stamatis Karnouskos	SAP Germany	2
Steen Brahe	IT University of Copenhagen	0
Stefan Appel	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Stefan Bachhofner	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Stefan Bloemheuvel	Tilburg University	0
Stefan Esser	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Stefan Fenz	Vienna University of Technology	0
Stefan Gruenwald	Campus 02 University of Applied Sciences	0
Stefan Jablonski	University of Bayreuth	0
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Stefan Mutke	University of Leipzig	0
Stefan Pottinger	IPL Information Processing Ltd	2
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Stefan Schöning	University of Bayreuth	0
Stefan Seidel	Liechtenstein University	0
Stefan Vielgut	University of Klagenfurt	0
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Stefan Zugal	University of Innsbruck	0
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Stefanie Betz	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Stefanie Lindstaedt	Know-Center Graz	1
Stefanie Rinderle-Ma	Ulm University	0
Stefanie Rinderle-Ma	University of Vienna	0
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Stefano Modafferi	Politecnico di Milano	0

Stefano Mon- tanelli	University of Milan	0
Stefano Savazzi	Aalto University	0
Stefano Soi	University of Trento	0
Stefano Tran- quillini	University of Trento	0
Steffen Staab	University of Koblenz-Landau	0
Steffi Donath	University of Leipzig	0
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Stephan Haar- mann	University of Potsdam	0
Stephan Kuehnel	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg	0
Stephan Poelmans	Vlekho Business School	0
Stephan Reiff- Marganiec	University of Leicester	0
Stephan Rudolph	Fraunhofer-Institut für Software- und Systemtech- nik	1
Stephan Sigg	Aalto University	0
Stephanie Meerkamm	University of Bayreuth	0
Stephanus Bu- diono	Queensland University of Technology	0
Stephen Corea	University of Warwick	0
Stephen Gorton	University of Leicester	0
Stephen Milliner	Queensland University of Technology	0
Stephen Rashford	Queensland Ambulance Service (QAS)	3
Steven Gross	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Steven Mertens	Ghent University	0
Stijn Goedertier	KU Leuven	1
Stéphane Moinard	Qualnet	2
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Suhwan Lee	Ulsan National Institute of Science and Technology	1
Sukriti Goel	Infosys Technologies Ltd	2
Suriadi Suriadi	Queensland University of Technology	0
Susana Alves	Technical University of Lisbon	0
Susanne Bülow	University of Potsdam	0
Susanne Gliss- mann	IBM Research United States	1
Susanne Patig	University of Bern	0
Sven Feja	Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel	0
Sven Fink	University of Augsburg	0

Sven Graupner	Hewlett Packard Labs	1
Sven Heiberg	Cybernetica AS	2
Sven Hellmann	OPITZ CONSULTING GmbH	2
Sven Till	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Syed M. Kumail Akbar	CKM Advisors	2
Sylvain Cherrier	UMR LIGM	1
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Szymon Wilk	Poznan University of Technology	0
Sérgio A. Rodrigues	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Sönke Knoch	Saarland University	0
Sören Auer	University of Leipzig	0
Søren Debois	IT University of Copenhagen	0
Tadeu Classe	Federal University of Rio de Janeiro	0
Taisiia Rogova	KU Leuven	1
Takahide Nogayama	IBM Research Japan	1
Talib Damij	University of Ljubljana	0
Tammo van Lessen	University of Stuttgart	0
Tao Peng	University of Trento	0
Tarek Melliti	University of Evry	0
Taïeb Mellouli	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg	0
Teemu Lehto	Aalto University	0
Tessa Rompen	Philips Research	1
Thamer Ba Dhafari	University of Leeds	0
Thanh Tran Thi Kim	ISIS-Papyrus	2
Tharaka Ilayperuma	Stockholm University	0
Theresa Schmiedel	Liechtenstein University	0
Theresia Gschwandtner	Vienna University of Technology	0
Thiemo Voigt	Swedish Institute of Computer Science	1
Thijs Hegge	KU Leuven	1
Thomas Bach	University of Stuttgart	0
Thomas Baier	University of Potsdam	0
Thomas Baier	BWI Systeme GmbH	2
Thomas Baier	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	0
Thomas Bauer	DaimlerChrysler AG	2

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Thomas Grace	University of the Witwatersrand	0
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Thomas Gschwind	IBM Research Switzerland	1
Thomas Heer	RWTH Aachen University	0
Thomas Hettel	Queensland University of Technology	0
Thomas Hille	University of Potsdam	0
Thomas K. Dasaklis	University of Piraeus	0
Thomas Keller	ZHAW School of Management and Law	0
Thomas Kleinert	Saarland University	0
Thomas Mikalsen	IBM Research United States	1
Thomas Molka	SAP Research United Kingdom	1
Thomas Molka	SAP United Kingdom	2
Thomas Neubauer	Secure Business Austria	2
Thomas Probst	Danube University Krems	0
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Thomas Stocker	University of Freiburg	0
Thomas T. Hildebrandt	IT University of Copenhagen	0
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Thomas Vogelgesang	University of Oldenburg	0
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Timothy McPhillips	University of California Davis	0
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Tobias Brückmann	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Tobias Freudenreich	Technical University of Darmstadt	0
Tobias Griebe	Software Engineering Group, University of Duisburg-Essen, paluno - The Ruhr	0
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Tobias Jakob	medrapid GmbH	2
Tobias Käfer	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Tobias Küster	Technische Universität Berlin	0
Tobias Seyffarth	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg	0
Tobias Unger	University of Stuttgart	0
Todor Stoitsev	SAP Germany	2
Tolga Bektaş	Başkent University	0
Tom Baeyens	Effektif GmbH	2
Tom Broens	Mobihealth BV	3
Tom Parsons	IBM Research United States	1
Tom Thaler	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz	1
Tom Thaler	Saarland University	0
Tomasz Kaczmarek	Poznan University of Economics	0
Tomer Sagi	Technion-Israel Institute of Technology	1
Ton Weijters	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Tong Sun	Xerox Corporation	2
Toni Ruokolainen	University of Helsinki	0
Tony Allard	Defence Science and Technology Group	2
Toomas Saarsen	University of Tartu	0
Toon Jouck	Hasselt University	0
Tor Neple	SINTEF	1
Tore Fjellheim	Queensland University of Technology	0
Tri A. Kurniawan	University of Wollongong	0
Tróndur Høgna-son	IT University of Copenhagen	0
Tsun Yin Wong	University of Potsdam	0

Tsuyoshi Kanai	Fujitsu Ltd.	2
Tytti Virtanen	Tampere University of Technology	0
Udo Kan-nengiesser	National ICT Australia	1
Ugur Cayoglu	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	1
Ujval Mysore	Infosys Technologies Ltd	2
Ulrich Frank	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Ulrich Kreher	Ulm University	0
Ulrike Kutscha	University Hospital Heidelberg	0
Umeshwar Dayal	Hewlett Packard Labs	1
Ustun Yildiz	UMR LORIA	1
Uttam Kumar Tripathi	Indian Institute of Management	1
Uwe Aßmann	Technical University Dresden	0
Uwe Glässer	Simon Fraser University	0
Uwe V. Riss	SAP Germany	2
Uwe Zdun	Vienna University of Business and Economics	0
Uwe Zdun	University of Vienna	0
Uwe Zdun	Vienna University of Technology	0
Vadim Denisov	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Valeria Becker	IBM Research United States	1
Valeria Herskovic	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	0
Valerie Jones	University of Twente	0
Vanessa Casanova-Brito	University of Bern	0
Vanessa Tavares Nunes	University of Brasilia	0
Vanisha Gokaldas	City, University of London	0
Varun Deshpande	Université Paris-Est (Paris XII)	0
Varvara Kalokyri	Rutgers University	0
Vasilios Andrikopoulos	University of Stuttgart	0
Vatcharaphun Rajsiri	EBM WebSourcing	2
Vatche Ishakian	IBM Research United States	1
Vera Künzle	Ulm University	0
Veronica Liesaputra	Unitec Institute of Technology	1
Verónica Peralta	Université Paris-Saclay	0
Vesko Detschew	Technische Universität Ilmenau	0
Viara Popova	University of Tartu	0
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Vicente Pelechano	Technical University of Valencia	0
Vicente Pelechano	Universitat Politècnica de València	0
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Victor Muntés-Mulero	CA Strategic Research, CA Technologies	1
Victor Vianu	University of California at San Diego	0
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Vinay Kulkarni	Tata Consultancy Services	2
Vincent Bloemen	University of Twente	0
Vincenzo Ferme	University of Lugano	0
Vinicius Stein Dani	Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul	0
Vinod Muthusamy	University of Toronto	0
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Viviane Jonckers	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	0
Vladimir Rubin	University of Paderborn	0
Vladimir Tasic	National ICT Australia	1
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Walid Gaaloul	UMR LORIA	1
Walid Gaaloul	UMR SAMOVAR	1
Walid Gaaloul	UMR Telecom SudParis	1
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Walter Schäfer	University of Siegen	0
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Wasim Sadiq	SAP Research Australia	1
Wassim Derguech	National University of Ireland	0
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Wei Zhou	ESCP Business School	0
Weimin Wu	Zhejiang University	0
Wendy MacCaull	St. Francis Xavier University	0
Werner Esswein	Technical University Dresden	0
Werner Nutt	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	0
Werner Rotzoll	DVZ Datenverarbeitungszentrum Mecklenburg-Vorpommern GmbH	2
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Werner Wild	Evolution Consulting	2
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Wil M. P. van der Aalst	RWTH Aachen University	0
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Wilfried Lemahieu	KU Leuven	1
Wilhelm Koop	University of Duisburg-Essen	0
Wilhelm Schäfer	University of Paderborn	0
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Winfried Schlee	Regensburg University	0
Witold Abramowicz	Poznan University of Economics	0
Wojtek Michalowski	University of Ottawa	0
Wolfgang Deiters	Fraunhofer-Institut für Software- und Systemtechnik	1
Wolfgang Groß	m2n consulting GmbH	2
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Wouter Joosen	KU Leuven	1
Wube Alemayehu	Ababa University	0
Xiang Gao	China Mobile Communications Corporation	2
Xiang Li	IBM Research China	1
Xiao Liu	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Xiao Liu	East China Normal University	0
Xiao-Jun Zeng	University of Manchester	0
Xiaofeng Xie	Hong Kong Baptist University	0
Xiaohui Zhao	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Xiaohui Zhao	University of Canberra	0
Xiaoliang Fan	Lanzhou University	0
Xiaonan Zhang	China Mobile Communications Corporation	2
Xifeng Yan	University of California at Santa Barbara	0
Xinwei Zhu	Wuhan University	0
Xiwei Xu	CSIRO	1
Xiwei Xu	National ICT Australia	1
Xixi Lu	University of Utrecht	0
Xixi Lu	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Y. Gorronogoitia	ATOS Research	1
Yael Dubinsky	IBM Research Israel	1
Yair Wand	The University of British Columbia	0
Yan Liu	National ICT Australia	1
Yang Qian	Hefei University of Technology	0
Yang Yu	Sun Yat-sen University	0
Yannick Frein	UMR G-SCOP	1
Yannis Theodoridis	University of Piraeus	0
Yannis Zоргios	CLMS (UK) LIMITED	2
Yao-Hua Tan	Delft University of Technology	0
Yaron Denekamp	Carmel Medical Center	2
Yasuki Iizuka	Tokai University	0
Yeguo Wang	Anhui University	0
Yezheng Liu	Hefei University of Technology	0
Yi Chen	Arizona State University	0
Yi Guo	Beijing Jiaotong University	0
Yiannis Verginadis	National Technical University of Athens	0
Yijun Yu	The Open University	0
Yikai Ren	University of South Australia	0
Ying Leung	IBM Research United States	1
Ying Wang	Beijing Jiaotong University	0

Ying Xie	Anhui University	0
Yiqin Yu	IBM Research China	1
Yoav Rubin	IBM Research Israel	1
Yolanda Rankin	IBM Research United States	1
Yongliang Cheng	Anhui University	0
Yotam Evron	University of Haifa	0
You-Wei Cheah	Indiana University	0
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Yuanchun Jiang	Hefei University of Technology	0
Yuanwei Zhu	Anhui University	0
Yudistira Asnar	University of Trento	0
Yun Yang	Swinburne University of Technology	0
Yurdaer Doganata	IBM Research United States	1
Yurong Chen	China Mobile Communications Corporation	2
Yutian Sun	University of California at Santa Barbara	0
Yuval Shahar	Ben Gurion University of the Negev	0
Zan Huang	The Pennsylvania State University	0
Zhao Xiangpeng	Peking University	0
Zhe Shan	The Pennsylvania State University	0
Zheng He	East China Normal University	0
Zheng Liu	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Zhili Zhao	Freie Universität Berlin	0
Zhiqiang Yan	Capital University of Economics and Business	0
Zhiqiang Yan	Eindhoven University of Technology	0
Zhiqiang Yan	Tsinghua University	0
Zizhe Ding	China Mobile Communications Corporation	2
Zongwei Luo	The University of Hong Kong	0
Zoran Marjanovic	University of Belgrade	0
Zoran Milosevic	Queensland University of Technology	0
Alvaro Valencia-Parra	University of Seville	0
Òscar Coltell	Universitat Jaume I	0
Özge Gürbüz	Middle East Technical University	0
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Ülari Laurson	University of Tartu	0
İmdat Kara	Başkent University	0

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